

ABSTRACT

Background: Sustainable Development Agenda is gaining importance by all countries. One of its targets is to end the epidemics of malaria and neglected vector-borne diseases. Acknowledging its importance right adaptation of interventions for housing as suggested by “Keeping the Vector Out” and the Global Vector Control Response 2017–2030 can make cities and human settlements vector proof and sustainable.

Objective: To assess community perceptions regarding chikungunya vector proof housing for sustainable development.

Methodology: Descriptive observational cross-sectional study was carried out that included 400 households of Aziz Bhatti Town, Lahore. Semi structured questionnaire administered by personal interview method to the one available and willing adult member of the household by researcher with environmental inspector and lady sanitary patrol of Dengue and Polio survey teams of Deputy District office Aziz Bhatti Town Lahore, using simple random sampling technique after consent and ethical approval. Questionnaire was pre-tested (Pilot), then the main survey was conducted. Data was entered and analyzed through SPSS 20.0.

Results: Among 400 households, 69.0% were 18-34 years. 53.5% were males, 47.0% were tenants, 69.7% were living in houses that were built ≥ 9 year. Climatic change and global warming was a matter of concern for 88.8% and 91.5% believed that increase mosquito borne disease and climatic change impact can be mitigated by improving housing. House design can prevent entry and breeding of mosquito reported by 95.4% but only 27.3% consider mosquito prevention interventions as one of the important factor when constructing their house. Although, 86.3% screened windows and eaves, 83.0% always checked cracks and crevices in the wall, floor and roof and cemented them, but 16.0% were undecided and 6.0% disagreed that Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika disease are spread by Aedes mosquito species, and 81.8% urged for health education regarding Chikunguniya vector proof housing. Regarding barriers, 73.5% could not afford modern building materials, as 73.5% also reported financial issues however 13.8% considered mosquito screen as an obstruction to ventilation. Suggesting, most

effective source of health information regarding chikunguniya vector proof housing was lady sanitary patrol, television and social media.

Conclusion: Housing improvement can mitigate the impacts of climatic change and vector borne disease. But health program planners need to identify and facilitate removal of barriers for adoption of vector proof housing.

Keywords: Community, Perceptions, Chikungunya, Vector Proof Housing, Sustainable Development

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Development Agenda is gaining importance by all countries. One of the targets for Sustainable Development Goal 3 is” good health and well-being” is to end the epidemics of malaria and neglected vector-borne diseases such as Chagas, Leishmaniasis, Dengue, Zika and Chikungunya. Acknowledging the importance of Sustainable Development, The Global Vector Control Response 2017–2030 recommends house improvements which can mitigate the impact of climatic change. World Health Organization has issued best practice statements supporting housing improvements and environmental management which highlights the importance of housing and living conditions as a barrier against vector borne diseases like Dengue and Chikungunya; “Keeping the vector out” is at the core of effective housing interventions to prevent vector borne disease which can be accomplished by vector proof housing strategy. Right adaptation of interventions such as house screening, installing a reliable water supply and reducing open water storage can help making housing, cities and human settlements vector proof and sustainable.¹

Housing of course, is much more than a controlled climatic environment. Improvements in housing structure are traditionally a key pillar of public health, less explored in mosquito control. House screening was the first intervention trialed in Italy after the link between malaria and mosquitoes was discovered. Screening homes was subsequently shown to reduce mosquito borne disease risk in United States of America (USA), South Africa and India and vector proof houses contributed to its elimination in the USA and Europe.^[2] Latest research indicate that well-built, modern housing can be protective in many tropical countries and vector proof features such as closed eaves i.e. the gap between the top of the wall and the over-hanging roof, brick walls, tiled or metal roofs, or ceilings can reduce the entry of mosquito in house. For the growing population there is a need to built healthy homes, for little additional cost, new infrastructure and housing projects can be planned, designed and developed with vector control in mind, making urban settlements and cities intrinsically vector proof and healthy.²

According to World Health Organization (WHO) vector-borne diseases are causing more than 700,000 deaths annually. Chikungunya is becoming a global problem and has been identified in nearly 40 countries. In 2016 there was a total of 349,936 suspected and 146,914 laboratory confirmed cases reported to the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) regional office in 2017, Pakistan continues to respond to an outbreak which started in 2016.³ Climate change impacted the transmission of vector-borne disease which account for 17% of the global burden of communicable diseases.⁴ Climate change and Global warming are one of the greatest environmental and health equity challenges of our times. Third world countries are least prepared for their impacts and are most at risk. El-Nino Southern Oscillation (ENSO) event in 2014-16 caused climatic changes making world a safe haven for pathogens such as *Aedes aegypti* (*Ae. Aegypti*) and *Aedes Albopictus* (*Ae. Albopictus*) and their vectors to emerge and propagate clusters of diseases activity.⁵ Among Asian countries Pakistan's precipitation is also under (ENSO) influence.⁶

Chikungunya virus is a mosquito-borne virus of the Togaviridae family which is small, spherical, enveloped, positive-strand RNA genome, about 60-70 nm diameter capsid.^{7, 8} Most commonly *Ae. Aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus* from the *Aedes* genus transmit it to humans⁹ causing a non-specific illness including high fever, severe joint pain, muscle pain, nausea, fatigue, headache and rash in infected individuals. While most people recover from the acute illness in 1–2 weeks, while some of them continue to suffer from chronic joint pain which may persist for weeks to years following infection.¹⁰⁻¹²

Both *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. Albopictus* have been discovered in large outbreaks of chikungunya. Where *Ae. aegypti* is confined to tropics and sub-tropics and *Ae. albopictus* also occurs in temperate and even cold temperate regions. *Ae. albopictus* has spread from Asia to become established in areas of Africa, Europe and the Americas In recent decades.¹³

The species *Ae. albopictus* develops in a wider range of water-filled breeding sites than *Ae. aegypti*, like stumps, tree holes, rock pools coconut husks, cocoa pods and bamboo, in addition to artificial containers like saucers beneath plant pots and vehicle tyres. This show that *Ae. albopictus* lives in diversity of habitats such as rural as well as peri-urban areas and shady city parks.¹³

Ae. aegypti shares the same artificial outdoor habitats as *Ae. albopictus* and is also more closely associated with human habitation and uses indoor breeding sites like flower vases, water storage vessels and concrete water tanks in bathrooms.¹³

WHO carried out phylogenetic analysis of chikungunya virus isolated from patients residing in Pakistan revealed that Pakistani strains shared high similarity with East/Central/South African, Indian Ocean Lineage (ECSA.IOL) and strains were closely related to those derived in India which suggests the possibility of their migration from India to Pakistan.¹⁴ It is crucial to assess the risk as to identify areas where specific public health measures, such as surveillance and vector control, can be implemented if further chikungunya outbreaks occur in Pakistan.¹⁴ Efforts to develop a vaccine against Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika, have been ongoing for decades but none is highly effective. Therefore, preventing or reducing transmission of Aedes-borne diseases depend entirely on control of the mosquito vectors or interruption of human-vector contact.¹⁵

Mosquito proof houses and hospital acts as a shield in transmitting infection from an immobilize person. It therefore raises the cost of virulence incurred by parasite making the cost benefit trade off for vector borne pathogen more like that for directly transmitted pathogen. Such improvements on broad geographic scale can make pathogen variant adversely enough remain in their vector proof structure would achieve virtually no propagation during the incapacitation illness. Field experiments are now needed to determine whether investment in mosquito proofing cause evolutionary reduction in pathogen virulence.¹⁶

To reduce the burden of mosquito borne disease and keeping in view the low awareness practices, study on Community perceptions regarding Chikungunya Vector Proof Housing in Lahore, Pakistan for Sustainable Development was carried out; that will help policy makers to understand the needs of community regarding vector proof housing infrastructure in light of World Health Organization guidelines, and prevent vector borne disease before another epidemic.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 HISTORY

Chikungunya disease was first detected in 1953 Newalla district, Tanzania, Africa. following an outbreak on the Makonde Plateau in a Swahili village.^{17,18} The virus was isolated from the serum of febrile patient. In reference to the stooped posture developed as a result of the arthritic symptoms of the disease, from the Makonde word kungunyala, meaning “that which bends up” Chikungunya derived its name. In Swahili, this means “the illness of the bended walker”.¹⁷

Chikungunya virus originated in the Central /East Africa,¹⁹ where the virus has been found to cycle between forest-dwelling mosquitoes and non-human primates in a sylvatic cycle. Currently, chikungunya fever has been identified in nearly 40 countries. Recent epidemics in Indian Ocean have led to the recognition that Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) is capable of moving into previously unaffected areas and causing significant levels of disease and human suffering.²⁰ US National institute of Allergy and Infectious Disease (NIAID) categorized Chikunguniya as a priority pathogen in 2008.¹⁷

2.2 DISEASE OUTBREAKS

Chikungunya occurs in Asia, Africa and the Indian subcontinent. For a number of years human infections in Africa remained at relatively low levels, but in 1999–2000 there was an epidemic in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and in Gabon in 2007.¹³

A major outbreak of chikungunya occurred in islands of the Indian Ocean starting in February 2005. A large number of imported cases in Europe were associated with this outbreak, In 2006 when the Indian Ocean epidemic was at its peak. A large outbreak of chikungunya in India occurred in 2006 and 2007. Several other countries in South-East Asia were also affected. Since 2005, the disease showed positive prevalence in many countries like Maldives, Myanmar, India, Indonesia, and Thailand reporting over 1.9 million cases. Europe for the first time reported its transmission in 2007; it was a localized outbreak in north-eastern Italy. During

this outbreak there were 197 cases recorded and it confirmed that there was positive prevalence of mosquito-borne outbreaks by *Ae. albopictus* in Europe.¹³

The first documented outbreak of chikungunya was in France, December 2013 where 2 laboratories confirmed autochthonous cases in the French part of the Caribbean island of St Martin were detected. Since then, continuous transmission has been confirmed in over 43 countries and territories in the WHO Region of the Americas 191 deaths have also been attributed to this disease during the same period. USA, Mexico and Canada have also recorded imported cases.¹³

On 21 October 2014, France confirmed 4 cases of locally acquired chikungunya infection in Montpellier. Currently chikungunya outbreak is ongoing in Cook Islands and Marshall Islands, while the number of cases in French Polynesia, Kiribati American Samoa and Samoa has reduced. WHO responded to small outbreaks of chikungunya in late 2015 in the state of Punjab India, the city of Dakar and Senegal.¹³

America in 2015, reported 693489 suspected cases and 37480 confirmed cases of chikungunya to the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) regional office, where Colombia marked highest 356079 suspected cases, this record if compared with 2014 marked less as during this period of time more than 1 million suspected cases were reported in the same region.¹³

If we see the disease record of chikunguniya during year 2016 there were total of 349,936 suspected and 146,914 laboratory confirmed cases reported to the PAHO regional office, almost half the burden compared to the previous year. Most of the cases were reported from Brazil (265000 suspected cases), Colombia and Bolivia (19000 suspected cases, respectively). Autochthonous transmission of chikungunya disease was for the first time that reported in Argentina 2016 following an outbreak of more than 1,000 suspected cases. In the African region, Kenya reported an outbreak of chikungunya resulting in more than 1700 suspected cases. Pakistan continues to respond to an outbreak in 2017 which began in 2016.

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2.3 CLINICAL DISEASE AND PATHOGENESIS OF CHIKUNGUNYA FEVER

CHIKV infected *Aedes* species mosquito is the major cause of Chikunguniya disease transmission to humans.²¹ When infected *Aedes* specie bites human CHIKV particles are thought to circulate through subcutaneous capillaries of the

skin and begin replicating in the fibroblasts of the dermis.²² Vitro studies have demonstrated that dendritic cells, natural killer cells and lymphocytes, are refractory to CHIKV infection.^{23,24} Within two to four days following infection, viral particles circulate to the circulatory system and disseminate to infect cells in other target organs, such as the muscles, liver, spleen and joints.²⁵ Chikunguniya less likely infects target cells in central nervous system, eye, liver and kidney.²⁶ After three to five days of infection, patients develop a viral load of approximately 10⁷ copies of RNA per milliliter serum, this concentration may persist in circulation for three to ten days.¹² Innate immune system produces natural defence system of type I interferons and signals that is attempting to control the spread of CHIKV replication which is directly correlated with the viral load in circulation. In most cases the innate and adaptive immunity mainly CHIKV-specific antibodies and CD4 T cells eradicate CHIKV replication in approximately 7 days.²¹

Patient of Chikunguniya fever experience “saddleback fever” characterized by a sudden onset of fever (on average 104°F) and relapse one to two days following a febrile period lasting four to ten days.²⁷ There may also be symptoms of severe polyarthralgia in the shoulders, spine, wrists, ankles, knees and elbows.²⁸ These events of polyarthralgia are characteristically symmetrical and bilateral and patients experience extreme swelling, tenderness, and may remain lethargic for several weeks or months.²⁹ Other symptoms include weakness, headache, myalgia, photophobia, retro-orbital pain, lumbar back pain, chills and petechial or maculopapular rash.²¹ Most acute symptoms resolve within seven to ten days of onset, Maculopapular rashes primarily appear on the trunk, face, and extremities two to five days post-infection and may last up to 10 days.^{28,30} Approximately 5-15% of patients experience an asymptomatic infection without revealed disease symptoms.³¹

Most of the acute symptoms of CHIKV resolve in one to two weeks, Sometimes large number of patients experience chronic arthritic symptoms which last from several months to years.³²⁻³⁴ Such patients are mostly elderly and have high viral loads, or already have some previously diagnosed, underlying medical conditions.^{32,33} These chronic symptoms may include: joint stiffness, bursitis, tenosynovitis arthralgia, myalgia, asthenia polyarthrititis and severe debilitating arthritis.¹² Although most Chikunguniya infections are not life threatening, recent

severe life-threatening symptoms have been described in the Indian Ocean epidemics (2006-2008) and America (2013-2016). Severe symptoms included heart failure and myocarditis, pneumonia and nephritis encephalitis, meningoencephalitis and Guillain-Barre syndrome.^{33,35-37} Although the percentage of such infections is among less than 1% of persons infected, mainly in the elderly or in patients with underlying health conditions about 280 fatalities have been recorded.³⁸

During the La Reunion Island outbreak vertical transmission of CHIKV from mother-to-child has been observed specifically in 2005.³¹ A research study conducted at the Groupe Hospitalier Sud-Reunion during outbreak found that mother-to-child transmission is rare with only 2.5% of exposed neonates becoming infected.³⁹

2.4 DIAGNOSIS OF CHIKUNGUNYA

Methods commonly used for diagnosis of chikunguniya are following.¹⁷

2.4.1: Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA):

Presence of IgM and IgG anti-chlorine antibodies are detected by these serologic tests. After the first week of onset of disease symptoms, both serological and virological methods are recommended for the test (RT-PCR).^{40,41}

2.4.2: Reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR):

These methods have variable sensitivity. Through this method we can also do gene typing of viruses, comparing virus samples from different geographical sources.⁴²

2.4.3: Immunofluorescence assays:

These tests can also quantify antibodies. However, proper training and specialized equipments are required.⁴³

2.4.4: Plaque reduction neutralization tests (PRNT):

These test are gold standard, need special laboratory equipment, they are specific for alpha virus.⁴⁴

2.4.5: Haemagglutination-inhibition test:

When the serum sample shows fourfold hemagglutination antibody difference along with the symptoms such as fever and joint pain, this test helps to differentiate chikungunya, strain which becomes positive within 5 to 8 days post infection.^{45,46}

2.4.6: POC (Point-Of-Care) Assays:

A reliable POC assay helps to differentiate between Dengue, Zika and Chikungunya virus, these tests are affordable and can be easily performed.^{47,17}

2.5 TREATMENT OF CHIKUNGUNYA

Till today no approved antiviral or vaccines are available for the CHIKV infection.⁴⁸ Recommended therapies include the use of supportive medicines such as analgesics, antipyretic and anti-inflammatory drugs like paracetamol and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs).⁴⁹ Aspirin is contraindicated due to the potential risk of bleeding or development of Reyes syndrome. In severe cases, where NSAIDs are not effective the disease modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) like methotrexate and sulfasalazine could be used.⁵⁰ For the treatment of chronic CHIKV arthritis chloroquine phosphate has long been reported to be effective as a supportive therapy.⁵¹

2.6 CLIMATIC CONDITIONS INFLUENCE ON MOSQUITO VECTORS

2.6.1: Seasonality of Infectious Diseases

Around the world the seasonal pattern of diseases like dengue fever and malaria vary.⁵² Mosquitoes are poikilothermic ectotherms; their body temperature depends on the temperature of surrounding.⁵³ The relationship between water temperature and development rate is analogous for eggs, larvae and pupae of the insects as described by the researchers.⁵⁴ At higher temperatures there is an increase in the rate of pupation, blood meals and a reduced incubation period, hence increasing the metabolism of mosquitoes and thereby causing an increase in the transmission of mosquito-borne diseases at higher temperatures.⁵³ Climatic factors like rainfall and precipitation affect the growth and development of mosquitoes; and viral replication within the vector.⁵² These strong links between multiple components of the

transmission cycle of vector-borne pathogens and the abiotic environment shows that climate change will affect the population dynamics of vector-borne diseases.⁵⁵

2.6.2: Vector-Borne Diseases

During a period of last 50 years global warming is affecting earth's climate, with an increase of surface, air and ocean temperature. Climatic variables that strongly influence Vector borne disease transmission are water-related, such as rainfall period, duration and abundance, and the humidity of the environment which are consequences of Global warming.⁵⁶

2.6.3: Temperature Sensitivity

For development of mosquito *Aedes* optimal temperatures are 22°C and 32°C. With higher temperatures having favorable survival range of *Ae.aegypti* its egg-laying time decreases, causing an increase in the population of mosquito. Development rates remain relatively stable above the optimal temperature, and begin to decrease until reaching the upper. This upper limit occurs at ~38 to 42°C,⁵⁷ Temperature of 39° C suppresses embryonic development and led to larval death within hours of hatching.^{58,59}

2.6.4: Precipitation Sensitivity

Changes in the level of precipitation is directly linked to the outbreak of infectious disease.⁶⁰ The metrological parameters such as humidity, temperature, precipitation (rainfall) and ENSO index have been linked with survival and reproduction of *Aedes* mosquitoes which are the major vector of mosquito borne disease. Precipitation has a great impact on the life cycle of *Aedes* mosquitoes as it facilitates aquatic stages of life cycle and promotes its population.⁶¹

2.6.5: Humidity Sensitivity

Air humidity is one of the factors that influence the development of mosquitoes. Humidity range between 81.5 to 89.5% is the optimal condition for the embryonation process and the survival of mosquito embryos. Low humidity cause evaporation of water from the mosquito's body. Humidity affects the process of mosquito breeding and mosquito flight distance an average temperature of 25

degree C -27 degree C with 60% -90% humidity is the optimum condition for mosquito breeding.⁶²

2.6.6: Sea Level Sensitivity

According to the researchers at the end of the 21st century, global warming is projected to increase sea levels by 18 to 59 cm through thermal expansion of seawater, polar ice, melting of glaciers.⁶³ The increase in sea level related to the change in climate results in the elimination or reduction of breeding sites for coastal wetland mosquitoes leading to decrease in their population.⁵² Due to recent meteorological conditions extreme cold temperatures, increase in extremely warm temperatures, rise in maximum sea levels and a significant increased cases of intense rainfall in various regions are common phenomenon and has the potential to significantly alter the future geographic range of mosquito vectors.⁶⁴

2.7 CONVENTIONAL METHODS USED TO CONTROL MOSQUITO POPULATIONS

2.7.1: Source Reduction (Environmental Control)

By preventing *Aedes* mosquito to breed on possible sites i.e source reduction.⁵² There is a varied range of breeding sites from bottle covers to water reservoirs. This method eradicates impermanent water tanks and closing permanent water reservoirs. This is mostly used as the first line of defence against mosquitoes such as *Ae. albopictus*, *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. atropalpus* that favour small- and medium-sized artificial water containers and tires placed in or around homes. Source reduction also affects the population of local mosquitoes like *Culex* spp. in the area by restraining the existing sites for process of laying eggs also called oviposition.⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷

Some breeding areas can be extremely beneficial for certain species. Example, for *A. albopictus* ridged extension fountains in USA, tank basins and tires in South Asia, and sinks in northern Italy. Source reduction, specifically for *Aedes* spp, needs to be consistent and recurrent; e.g frequent cleaning of water containers/vessels for daily use. Success depends largely on community participation like owner and public awareness. In a study in Brazil, nylon nets were used against *Aedes Aegypti* to shelter the most breeding sites such as water containers and metal barrels that resulted in a long-lasting drop in female

mosquito populations, showing the effectiveness of targeting preferable breeding sites. Unfortunately, this method does not assist in tracing hidden breeding sites, which are often unseen or inaccessible such as natural reservoirs including leaf litter.^{68,69}

2.7.2. Trapping (Mechanical Control)

One of the method of mechanical control is mass trapping which commonly uses odor to attract mosquitoes. Ovitrap or sticky gravid traps for trapping *Aedes* gravid females are used. Bio agent-sentinel traps are used for host-seeking females, the. The use of bioagent-sentinel traps is commonly inadequate due its need for electrical supply to work. Ovitrap shows the behavior of *Aedes* mosquitoes to lay their eggs in small containers. Insecticide-treated egg-laying strips are also being used.^{70,71} Ovitrap have been improved to enhance their effectiveness, like the use of organic infusions (grass, hay and oak) application. Gravid autocidal traps release water vapour and volatile attractant at a higher rate, thereby improving mosquito collection.⁷² These are designed such that a repellent is combine with some attractive tandem this is an effective control method against various mosquitoes. Although, materials treated with insecticides and residue spraying methods do not target mosquitoes like *Ae. albopictus* which are exophilic.^{72,73} CDC (dry ice CO₂) traps also capture mosquitoes effectively.^{74,75}

2.7.3: Insecticides (Chemical Control)

When physical and biological methods fail to keep mosquitoes at low threshold chemical control helps in instant reduction of mosquito population also called insecticide. Another class of insecticide is Larvicides which when applied directly to water it controls larvae populations. Whereas Adulticides along with synergists are used in reducing adult mosquitoes density.⁵²

In the twentieth century, the primary artificial organic insecticide that has been used for active malaria control by decreasing the life span of gravid female mosquitoes was dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (commonly known as DDT). Whereas Pyrethroids and insect growth regulators were effective compounds used worldwide in mosquito control approaches, as methoprene pyriproxyfen and diflubenzuron possessed adulticides and larvicides along with ovicidal properties.⁷⁶

Female *Aedes* are manipulated in variety of ways to reduce its population like auto-dissemination process which consists of manipulating female mosquitoes by contamination with insecticide (pyriproxyfen) through treated nets or diffusion stations designed from modified ovitraps. This method resulted in inducing high mortality rates of *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus* at the pupal stage. Moreover, the production and hatchability of eggs has also been affected by the same method. Another new approach is to synergize the sterile insect technique (SIT) with auto-dissemination which makes male mosquito sterile with pyriproxyfen to infect females during mating.⁷⁷

Ecologically friendly insecticides were also invented, which are purely plant-based and pay more attention to their safety, accessibility and environmental friendliness. Pesticides contained in plants can be used to reduce insect outbreaks. In chemical ecology, a study of the mechanism of functioning of allelochemicals found, that these allelochemicals have a protective mechanism which affects the central nervous system of the vector, like the synthesis of neurotransmitters, their conservation and release, and the binding of receptors and metabolic pathways.^{78,79}

The secondary metabolites of plants such as (phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, sterols, terpenes, carotenoids etc.) have their role in protecting plant themselves against microbial parasites and arthropods; e.g. against adult *Ae. aegypti*, *Calocedrus decurrens*, *Juniperus occidentalis* and *Eucalyptus tereticornis* against established *Anopheles stephensi*, *Chloroxylon swietenia* against *Anopheles gambiae*, *Culex quinquefasciatus*.⁵²

Plant extracts are more complex and include different chemicals than synthetic insecticides, so the physiological and behavioral action of botanical insecticides prevents the development of resistance to them, however, still in the research phase.⁵²

2.7.4: Biological Control

Recently bio-pesticides are becoming popular due to their safety and environmental friendly nature. Where bacteria, fungi, virus, fish and protozoa were found to be beneficial biopesticide regarding mosquito. Due to their limited availability they were not considered effective regarding mosquito control program. Spore forming bacteria, like *Bacillus sphaericus* Neide and *B.*

thuringiensis serovar israelensis deBarjac have been studied against Aedes mosquito populations that have been found to be toxic to these mosquito species. The spores of B. thuringiensis serovar israelensis deBarjac are carrying out a wider range of activities against Aedes. spp., Culex, and Anophels Bs, which are highly specific to individual species and act only against some species of Ae and especially Culex.⁵²

Two insecticidal proteins from B. sphaericus , BinA with 42 kDa and BinB with 51 kDa (known as binary toxin btx) were found to be highly toxic to mosquitoes. These toxins separately confirmed that BinA is extremely toxic at high doses without the need for BinB, but only BinB is not toxic. However, if at the same concentrations, they are extremely toxic to larvae. When mosquito larvae swallow btx, BinA and BinB dissolve in the intestines, where proteases convert them into 39 kDa and 43 kDa proteins. After conversion, these active proteins join the receptor on the mid-intestinal membrane, where inflammation of the mid-intestinal margin causes insect death.⁸⁰

For mosquito control, protein groups of Bti bacteria include cytolysines and deltaendotoxin crystals.⁶⁹ There are four type of polypeptides in Bti toxins called: “68 kDa, cit A ,28 kDa”, IVA crystals 125 kDa, IVB crystals 135 kDa, and IVD crystals. The plasmid of bacteria contains the genes which carry codes for these proteins. The Cry proteins have receptors in specific areas of midgut of mosquito, when they bind to these receptors they form pores and affect osmotic balance causing the paralysis of mosquito intestine and its death in an hour.⁵²

Still vectors have developed resistance against these insecticides by increase of evolutionary rate leading to large number of growth, short generation time and higher genetic variability among local species.⁵²

2.7.5: Genetic Control

Currently as compare to the conventional methods genetic approaches are becoming popular for mosquito control. Genetic methods affect mosquito virulence via mating. Target mosquito becomes modified by introducing heritable factors into target species so that the modified mosquito acts as bio-control .Such genetic strategies brings change in vector population in the form of affects like

population suppression, population replacement and other key aspects of genetic element persistence.⁸¹

Population of vector decreases in population suppression programs, which works on the strategy of insecticide. For example, sterile male are produced in sterile-male program which when mates with the controlled females results in their death eventually leading to the decrease in mosquito population.⁵² Population replacement methods decrease the midgut transmission capability of all of the mosquitoes present in the target population.^{82,83}

When the technique of sterile male system is used, such type of gene is produced which has undergone mutation or are inheritably lethal affecting only female offspring.^[84,85] Insect birth control or The Sterile Insect Technique (SIT), produces sterile male mosquitoes by radiation, which when mates with female does not produce any offspring. Hence, mosquito population declines with the passage of time. Now a day's researchers are emphasizing on this technique, as they think that controlling mosquito populations is currently the only measure which decrease the incidence of mosquito borne diseases such as Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika.⁸⁶

Other good examples of systems with DNA interventions are that of Wolbachia, transposons, synthetic Medea-like elements and the Homing Endonuclease Gene (HEG).^{87,88} In the same context to produce mosquitoes with a diminished capacity to transmit malaria or dengue researchers are working on Medea-like elements originating from the naturally present selfish Medea elements of *Tribolium castaneum* but such mosquitoes produced are not completely fit to mate and bring desired affects in population therefore such research is under process.⁸⁹ Female mosquito having wolbachia strains are transmitted from altered female mosquito to her offspring thereby producing male mosquitoes thereby reducing vector borne disease.⁵²

2.7.6: Integrative Vector Management Approach

Integrative Vector Management Approach (IVM) is a process based on situation analysis, monitoring and evaluation, surveillance and capacity building adopted by the public health experts to make optimum use of the resources for the control of mosquitoes by use of chemical, biological and physical methods.^{52,60}

2.8 VECTOR PROOF HOUSING

2.8.1: Historical Use of Housing as a Malaria Intervention

Vector proof housing trace its history back to Angelo Celli, 1899 who gave the concept of screening house. He gave protection to families against Malaria by screening their homes in Rome nearon families' resident near malarious railway line. Results of the study showed that nearly all families in the unprotected home had malaria, compared with only four malaria cases among 24 people who were living in protected homes. In 1900, he extended his work to other parts of the railway where some intervention homes were screened. In this study there were 96% fewer malaria cases in the protected group than among the controlled ones.⁹⁰

These studies spread the concept of improved housing against vector borne disease and this piece of information spread to different parts of the world like Europe and the United States of America. Europeans living in the tropics, and those workers building the Panama Canal used this concept in 1910 widely to protect themselves. In 1921, a malaria survey in Missouri, USA found that households of well screened houses had comparatively less malaria than those who lived in concrete home without screens (5% versus 12% respectively).⁹⁰ Houses which were poorly built were modified by screening however some of the entry points were left even then it reduced the rate of malaria. The incidence of malaria reduced from 613 per 1,000 to 48 per 1,000 between 1925-27, among the British barracks in Amritsar, India upon screening.⁹¹ A study in Alabama, USA in 1930 showed significant reduction in incidence of disease as a result of screening 700 homes as compared to control ones. Comparison showed that screened houses had a mean of 5.7 *Anopheles quadrimaculatus* compared with 8.0 in unprotected houses. Through the middle of the century vector proof houses continued to be recognized as a highly effective remedy against mosquito, even with the emergence of indoor residual spraying to fight against malaria their importance remained the same. Among the most practical, economical, and effective measures against malaria vector proof housing strategy was considered to be of worth as expressed by C. C. Kiker in 1941.⁹⁰

Today, there is compelling evidence that improved housing helps protect against mosquito borne disease in sub-Saharan Africa.^{92,93} Two latest analytic reviews bears strong evidence regarding this.^{2,94} A systematic review and meta-analysis

assessed whether improved housing had association with decrease risk of mosquito borne disease than traditional houses. The research concluded that 90 studies that measured the association between housing and mosquito borne disease. Overall, people living in modern houses had 47% lower odds of malaria vector borne disease as compare to the residents of traditional houses. Due to certain limitations the overall strength of the study was judged to be low.². A multi-country analysis of 15 Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) and 14 Malaria Indicator Surveys (MIS) between 2008 and 2015 in 21 countries in sub-Saharan Africa showed that modern housing was associated with 9-14% reduction in the odds of mosquito borne disease,⁹⁴ which was similar to the level of protection as seen with Long Lasting Insecticidal Nets. Both major studies favoured support for improved housing against malaria in sub-Saharan Africa.⁹⁰

Kirby and colleagues conducted a study to assess whether houses with either full screening of windows and doors, and closed eaves, or installation of screened ceilings could reduce the frequency of anemia in children in the Gambia. Children had 47% reduction in anemia due to decrease mosquito density indoor who lived in full screened houses, as compared to children living in the controlled houses. Full screened houses had 54%, reduction in mosquito density indoor as compared to the controlled houses.⁹⁵

A study in Uganda was conducted and it was found that in addition to the use of IRS (indoor residual spraying) people who were living in mosquito modified houses had 46% lower odds of malaria infection as compared to those who were despite of using IRS were living in traditional houses.⁹⁶ It suggests that housing improvements along with the use of IRS has additional benefits and leads to decrease in transmission of malaria providing long-term solution to malaria transmission.⁹⁰

2.8.2: Mosquito House Entry

About 80-100% of mosquito borne disease transmission in sub-Saharan Africa is affected by house construction. House is a place where men mostly get infected. it is the place where the risk mosquito and other vector-borne disease is highest.⁹⁰

If the openings are left in the infrastructure of house mosquitoes can easily find their way to enter the house. Being attracted by intermittent odours plumes such as carbon dioxide,⁹⁹ pouring out of a house.⁹⁸ Mosquito approaches the house at the

level of the open eaves.¹⁰⁰ Other risk factors include increased vector-density indoors including unscreened doors , open eaves, and windows.⁹⁰

2.8.3: Open Eaves

Evidence suggest that open eaves, the gap between the top of the wall and the over hanging roof, is the main route by which mosquito easily finds its way into the house in sub-Saharan Africa. An observational cross sectional descriptive study revealed that children who slept in houses with closed eaves had 20% less malaria as compare to those who lived in houses with open eaves.⁹⁰ In a study on risk factors for house-entry by malaria vectors in houses in a rural town and satellite villages of Gambia it was observed that houses with closed eaves had 43.2% fewer mosquitoes as compared with open eaves houses.¹⁰¹ houses that had closed eaves had 29% fewer *An. gambiae* s.l. compared to houses with open eaves. Study in rural Gambia explores the protective effect of closing eaves as such huts had 37% fewer *An. gambiae* in huts as compared with huts having open eaves.⁹⁸ Protective role of close eaves is evident from the study conducted in Gambia showing the least number of mosquitoes caught i.e 65% from such houses.¹⁰² Such study is supported by the generalized findings from the study conducted in southern Tanzania¹⁰³ where houses of the village with close eaves had 34% reduction in *An. gambiae* s.l. caught indoor as compared with houses having open eaves.⁹⁰

2.8.4: Ceilings

In rural Gambia when an experimental hut was created with screened ceilings it was found that the number of mosquito species of Malaria reduced by 78-80% compared with huts without ceilings.⁹⁸ Similar results were reported from Kenya, where ceilings made from papyrus mats reduced house entry of *Anopheles gambiae* by 78-80% and *An. funestus* densities by 86% as compared to those houses which were unmodified ones.¹⁰⁴ In Randomised controlled trials conducted by Kirby and colleagues Unmodified houses were associated with relatively higher densities of malaria vectors.⁹⁵ When ceilings are screened they reduce the number of mosquitoes entering the house by 40% as compare to control houses lacking a ceiling. House becomes likes an odour-baited trap, with mosquitoes that

enter the house through the open eaves being unable to pass through the screened ceiling to bite people sleeping in the room.⁹⁰

2.8.5: Screening

Screening being traditionally used for Malaria vector shows its importance in reducing mosquito borne disease.⁹⁰ In Tanzania experimental hut reduced the entry of Anophele mosquito by 57-63% as compared to unscreened houses.¹⁰⁵ A randomized control trial carried out recently shows that screened doors and windows reduced house entry of mosquito by 54%.⁹⁵ Another randomized control trial in south-west Ethiopia regarding screening of windows and doors shows that eaves closure reduced the indoor density of mosquito.¹⁰⁶

2.9 COMMUNITY PERCEPTIONS REGARDING CHIKUNGUNYA VECTOR PROOF HOUSING

Climatic change, vector borne disease emergence and housing improvements are closely linked to one another, by adopting Vector proof housing guidelines of World Health Organization one can mitigate the effects of climate change and achieve protection from disease i.e. screening windows, doors and eaves of houses, by fitting ceilings, filling the cracks and crevices in walls, floors and roofs, installing reliable supply of piped water, making sanitary facilities adequate etc. Among the highlights of Eighth meeting of the World Health Organization 2018; WHO document “Keeping the vector out” housing improvements for vector control and sustainable development was discussed furthermore, Professor Lindsay presented the findings of his research regarding systematic review on malaria, housing and household randomized controlled studies, and it was recommended to include housing improvements in intervention types and classes ; in the evaluation process for vector control products.¹

In Research study of Rashid and teammates (2018), to ascertain the knowledge and awareness regarding Chikungunya among community people of Dhaka city, Bangladesh. 266 participants were enrolled. Study revealed that although about (92.5%) of the respondents had heard of Chikungunya infection but only (50%) had knowledge about its transmission by Aedes mosquito. Among total participants, (47%) had misconceptions that Chikungunya vector breeds in dirty storage water. And only (43%) of the participants had correct knowledge about

the breeding habitat of *Aedes* mosquito. Respondents were conscious about the clinical symptoms of Chikungunya infection like joint pain (14.6%) and high fever (18.0%). Most of the respondents i.e 88% believed that Chikungunya disease is preventable. Various methods were used by the respondents as preventive practices like insecticide spray (19.3%), mosquito coils (15.1%), mosquito nets (28.4%), electric bat (12.4%) and window net (12.4%) for mosquito bite prevention. The most important and useful source of information regarding Chikungunya disease was considered to be social media. Study concluded that community needs Health education regarding Chikungunya in depth.⁷

A study was conducted by Feldstein and fellows (2018) when chikungunya virus outbreak in the United States Virgin Islands (USVI) occurred to assess household and individual-level mosquito prevention methods. During study 334 respondents were interviewed. Study revealed that majority (80%) of participants used screens on their windows of homes but still (82%) had an experience of the presence of mosquitoes despite of using screens. Due to infrequent adherence to individual- and household-level mosquito bite prevention measures in the USVI, these findings probe the need for improved public health education and investment in therapeutic and vaccine research to mitigate vector-borne disease outbreaks.¹⁰⁷

Dhaduk and coworkers (2013) undertook a study among 450 households to assess houses and knowledge, attitude, practice among residents of Jamnagar district, India regarding mosquito control measures. Study concluded that domestic environment provided favorable atmosphere for mosquito breeding. Majority had lack of knowledge regarding breeding places of mosquitoes, sign and symptoms of mosquito borne disease and their types. There was lack of active mosquito surveillance activity in urban areas and very poor in rural and slum area. The health care providers in the community neither educated community regarding disease nor screened them. Almost half of the community members were practicing at least one personal protective and larvae control measure, but less efficient one. Researchers concluded that KAP studies are necessary in terms of community participation so that people could be addressed about the details of mosquito prevention practices for effective mosquito control in community.¹⁰⁸

A study was performed by Sharma and associates (2017), in Mahaveer Nagar, Govt. Medical College, Kota, India. Regarding knowledge, attitude and practices regarding mosquito borne diseases among people. Total 966 households were

surveyed. Discussing mass media, (88.4%) respondents considered television and newspaper as the main source of information regarding mosquito borne disease. Most of respondents had no concept of frequently checking air coolers and emptying them. Most of them used mat, coil and liquid vaporizer during night time. Regarding sign and symptoms of disease, (97.16%) considered fever as chief complaint but rarely they had idea about the breeding place of mosquito according to their opinion mosquito breeds in dirty water. Study recommended to improve the level of knowledge among people by communication campaign so that the burden of mosquito borne diseases can be reduced. ¹⁰⁹

A study was done in (2018) by Kaindoa and comrades in rural Tanzanian villages, regarding assessment of influence of physical characteristics of houses and surrounding environments on mosquito biting risk, and to examine the relationship of between mosquito borne disease with community knowledge and their perceptions. Kaindoa, found that modern housing with brick walls had less indoor mosquito densities as compared to mud made houses, quite similar results were found with open eaves compared and unscreened windows compared to screened windows and closed eaves. Respondents observed that their house allow mosquito entry, at least partially. Participants positively agreed that house structure and environmental characteristics affects indoor mosquito densities and consequently transmission of mosquito-borne diseases. Community was concerned about living in old design constructed houses with gaps on eaves, walls, windows and doors their financial issues were hindering them to make their house a vector proof structure. ¹¹⁰

In Lhasa, Tibet, Liu and his colleagues conducted a study (2014) to understand the relation between knowledge and experience with mosquito prevention practices and control of disease. The study found that the majority of respondents were 46 years old out of them (61.8%) were women. With regard to mosquito control and prevention practices (91.9 per cent), the respondents stated that mosquito control was necessary in summer. About 77.2% of those surveyed had used mosquito prophylaxis. Detailed protection measures included mosquito kill aerosols (21.5 per cent), mosquito nets (4.3 per cent), mosquito coils (50.4 per cent), door and window screens (49.3 per cent), stagnant water removal (9.4 per cent), repellent media (41.9 per cent), long-sleeved clothing (41.0 per cent), light traps (2.9 per

cent), Tibetan incense (2.0 per cent) and other means (4.3 per cent). The study concluded high level of knowledge, experience and practice of in Lhasa City.^[111] Among indigenes of Godokpe, Konlan and colleagues (2019) performed a study to examine the awareness of mosquito prevention practices; it was a rural community in the Municipality of Ghana. Study enrolled 246 residents 18 years of age and above. Study demonstrated that about (54%) of the respondents had satisfactory and (20%) of them had good levels of knowledge regarding mosquito prevention. The methods used for prevention included mosquito net (59%), mosquito coils (72%), mosquito spray (54%), cleaning and prevention of water stagnation (62%), The major sources of information regarding disease were television (74%), ,schools (62%), the Internet (51%) and family/friends (60%). Study concluded that school children had good knowledge about the control of Vector.¹¹²

Farkhanda Manzoor and Colleagues (2017) reported the confirm presence of the two species of mosquitoes *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* from different localities of Lahore i.e Aziz Bhatti Town, Wahga Town, Shalimar Town.¹¹³

Abdul waheed khan and his colleague (2018) also studied current status of chikunguniya virus. In urban areas, *Ae. Aegypti* were mostly found in discarded tyre ruts made in unsealed road surfaces and small water containers in close proximity to residential housing.¹¹⁴

EM Qureshi and Colleagues conducted descriptiveobservational cross sectional study in one union council of Samnabad, Lahore city on 600 households about their perceptions regarding vector borne disease. As people were already aware about the hazards of storing water in open containers it was easier for the researcher to motivate them regarding use of piped water supplies, about 54.1% reported that they stored water in close containers. Regarding mass media as the source of information against vector borne disease television and radio was one of the main sources of information about symptoms, spread, prevention and control of mosquito borne disease.¹¹⁵

Wilson and team mates (2015) conducted descriptive observational cross sectional study regarding mosquito borne diseases. Among patients attending Western Jamaica hospital, large proportion of the respondents (80%) did not used mosquito screen/mesh on the windows, regarding water storage containers (39%) reported covering them while (39%) reported emptying water containers frequently.

Secondly, homeowners were (65%) less concern regarding keeping their home and immediate surrounding clean as compare to renters, may be because renters have obligation to maintain their hygiene in order to prevent problems with their landlords and other tenants. Study can be used to develop interventions designed to improve vector control. ¹¹⁶

CHAPTER 3

3.1 OBJECTIVE

- To assess community perceptions regarding chikungunya vector proof housing.

3.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Pakistan as a member of global community needs to move ahead and progress towards attainment of Sustainable Development Goals more specifically related to the well being and health of population, reduction of poverty, hunger, improvement of sanitation, improvement of environment, participation of people in development agenda and social inclusion. The available data of Pakistan describes the prevalence and knowledge, attitude, practices of people towards vector borne disease. The studies on effectiveness of vector proof housing are limited. This study highlights the perceptions of people in Aziz Bhatti Town Lahore regarding vector proof housing against Aedes mosquito responsible for the spread of Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika, and also the gaps in communication channels regarding health education, will ultimately help policy makers, various stakeholders, experts in the field and general public about the prevailing situation for needed interventions. Thereby with little additional cost, new infrastructure and housing projects can be planned, designed and developed with vector control in mind, helping to make urban settlements and cities intrinsically vector proof and sustainable.

3.3 OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Vector Proof Housing

Vector proof house is an effective housing intervention to prevent the entry of disease-transmitting vector into human habitation by screening windows, doors and eaves of houses, by fitting ceilings, and by reducing the vectors' indoor hiding and breeding places, such as cracks and crevices in walls, floors and roofs. Such building strategies need to be accompanied with improved ventilation, to keep the occupants cool in hot climates.

Perception

Perceptions will be measured using semi structured questionnaire. Responses will be taken on Likert scale of 1 to 5 given to each perception, varying from:

SA = Strongly Agree **A** = Agree **UN** = Undecided **D** = Disagree
SD = Strongly Disagree

CHAPTER 4

MATERIAL AND METHODS

4.1 STUDY DESIGN

Descriptive Cross Sectional Study

4.2 SETTING

To determine household perceptions regarding chikungunya vector proof housing. Aziz Bhatti town was chosen for exploration. Town is located 18.4km next to Wahga Border having 705311 population chosen as area of interest due to positive prevalence of genus Aedes mosquito and least studied by the reserchers. Study conducted in 13 Union Councils of Aziz Bhatti town an administrative town (tehsil) in Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan, with the consent of Deputy District office Lahore as here community needs sensitization.

4.3 STUDY DURATION

The duration of the study was 9 months after the approval of synopsis.

4.4 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Simple Random Sampling technique

4.5 SAMPLE SIZE

Population of Aziz Bhatti Town according to the document (Annexure 9.3) provided by District Health Department, Aziz Bhatti Town Lahore on July 2019 is 705311.

We calculated the population size using the Taro Yamane formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^{[2]}}$$

where n= Sample size

N=Population Size

e=Sampling of error i.e. ±5%

Therefore the sample size of the target population is

$$n = 705311 / 1 + [705311(0.05)]^{[2]}$$

n= 400 households.

4.6 SAMPLE SELECTION

Inclusion Criteria

- Respondent of both gender 18-60 years of age, members of family interviewed.

Exclusion Criteria

- Respondent living in area for a period less than 6 months.
- Respondent with Mental disability.
- Respondent with dementia.

4.7 DATA COLLECTION TOOL

Data was collected using a Semi structured questionnaire administered by personal interview method to the one available and willing adult member of the household. The questionnaire formulated according to the World Health Organization guidelines “Keeping the Vector Out, 2017”(Chikunguniya/Dangue specific) to improve housing sector and to mitigate the effect of climatic change and protection from diseases for sustainable development. The questionnaire was first translated by the researcher from English to Urdu language and pre-tested (Pilot) before conducting the main survey to check its precision on 10% of the study population i.e 40 respondents who were households residing in the same area but were not the part of the study sample (Annexure 9.7). After pilot study no changes were made and the main survey was conducted.

The questionnaire covered the following areas: (I) Socio-demographic information (Name, sex, age, education, house ownership and employment); (II) Knowledge about climatic change link to Chikunguniya vector proof housing; (III) Perceptions about practices regarding Chikunguniya vector proof housing using (Likert’s 5 point scale); (IV) Chikunguniya vector proof housing practice barriers (V) Health education regarding Chikungunya vector proof housing.

4.7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The ethical aspects of the project entitled “Community Perceptions regarding Chikungunya Vector Proof Housing in Lahore, Pakistan for Sustainable Development.” A cross sectional study undertakings by Dr.Serena Taj student of Masters of Philosophy in Public Health at IPH, University of Lahore, to observe the condition regarding the ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects as;

- Written informed consent (attached) was taken from all the participants.
- All information and data collection was kept confidential.
- The subjects were informed that there are no disadvantages or risks on the procedure of the study.
- They were also informed that they will be free to withdraw at any time during the process of the study.
- There was no known risk associated with this research.
- There were benefits to the participant that would result from their participation in this research.
- Measures were taken to protect the privacy. The identity was not revealed in any publication resulting from this study.
- Your participation in this research study is voluntary. You may choose not to participate and you may withdraw your consent to participate any time. You will not be penalized in any way should you decide not you participate or to withdraw from this study.

4.8 DATA COLLECTION

It was a quantitative study, simple random sampling technique was used to collect data of a sample of 400 households in 13 Union Councils of Aziz Bhatti town, map attached (Annexure 9.4), between October 2019 to January 2020 using Computer generated random number list of household obtained from the Database of District Health Department Aziz Bhatti Town Lahore attached (Annexure 9.6). Semi structured questionnaire was administered by personal interview method to the one available and willing adult member of the household. If the house was not located or household member refused to participate, the member of the next household according to the list provided was interviewed until reaching the sample size required. The interviews were conducted by researcher with help of environmental inspector and lady sanitary patrol of Dengue and Polio survey teams of Deputy District Office Aziz Bhatti Town Lahore.

The questionnaire first translated by the researcher from English to Urdu language and pre-tested (Pilot) before conducting the main survey to check its precision on 10% of the study population i.e 40 respondents who were households residing in the same area but were not the part of the study sample (Annexure 9.7). After pilot study no changes were made and the main survey was conducted.

4.9 DATA ANALYSIS

Data was analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 20.0. Frequency and percentage tables were generated for all possible variables related to categorical data. Bar and pie diagrams were used in the same context.

CHAPTER 5

RESULTS

5.1: Frequency distribution of respondents According to age

Among 400 respondents, 276 (69.0%) were 18-34 years old, 98 (24.5%) were 35-49 years old and 20 (5.0%) were 50-64 years old while only 6 (1.5%) respondents were 65 years old and above.

Age	Frequency (%)
18-34 years	276 (69.0)
35-49 years	98(24.5)
50-64 years	20(5.0)
65 years and above	6(1.5)
Total	400

**Table 1: Frequency distribution of respondents
According to age**

5.2: Frequency distribution of respondents According to sex

Among 400 respondents, 214 (53.5%) were males and 186 (46.5%) were females.

Sex	Frequency (%)
Male	214(53.4)
Female	186(46.5)
Total	400(100.0)

**Table 2: Frequency distribution of respondents
According to sex**

5.3: Distribution of respondents According to educational status

The educational status of 400 households, that among 400 respondents, 7 (1.8%) were illiterate, 95 (23.8%) studied upto primary (Grade-5), 162 (40.5%) had secondary education, 130 (32.5%) studied upto university level and 6(1.4%) respondents had technical education.

Figure 1: Frequency distribution of respondents According to educational status

5.4: Distribution of respondents According to house ownership

The frequency distribution of 400 households with respect to their house ownership, it states that 212(53.0%) were house-owners, while 188 (47.0%) respondents were tenants.

Figure 2: Frequency distribution of respondents According to house ownership

5.5: Frequency distribution of respondents According to housing type

Among 400 respondents, 347 (86.8%) were living in houses built with concrete, 53 (13.2%) in mix type houses i.e Bricked (Brick masonry style) and concrete material.

Housing type	Frequency (%)
Concrete	347(86.8)
Mix (Bricked/Concrete)	53(13.2)
Total	400(100)

**Table 3: Frequency distribution of respondents
According to housing type**

5.6: Frequency distribution of respondents According to employment

Among 400 respondent, 281 (70.2%) were employed and 119 (29.8%) were unemployed.

Employment	Frequency (%)
Employed	281(70.2)
Unemployed	119(29.8)
Total	400(100)

**Table 4: Frequency distribution of respondents
According to employment**

5.7: Frequency distribution of respondents According to number of children

Among 400 respondents, 84 (21.0%) had no child while 153 (38.2%) had 1-2 children and 163 (40.8%) respondents had 3 children or more.

Children	Frequency (%)
None	84(21.0)
1-2	153(38.2)
≥ 3	163(40.8)
Total	400(100.0)

**Table 5: Frequency distribution of respondents
According to number of children**

5.8: Frequency distribution of respondents According to total members in household

Among 400 respondents, 136 (34.0%) had 1-4 household members and more than half 264 (66.0%) had 5 members or more in the family.

Total in household	Frequency (%)
1-4	136(34.0)
≥ 5	264(66.0)
Total	400(100.0)

**Table 6: Frequency distribution of respondents
According to total members in household**

5.9: Frequency distribution of respondents According to age of house

Among 400 respondents, 70 (17.5%) were living in houses that were upto 4 years old, 51 (12.8%) were living in 5-8 years old houses and 279 (69.7%) respondents living in houses that were built 9 year before or more.

Age of house	Frequency (%)
≤4 years age	70(17.5)
5-8 years age	51(12.8)
≥9 years age	279(69.7)
Total	400(100.0)

**Table 7: Frequency distribution of respondents
According to age of house**

5.10: Knowledge About Climatic Change Link To Chikungunya Vector Proof Housing

Among respondents, 355 (88.8%) believed that climatic change and global warming is a matter of concern for them, 361 (90.2%) believed that disease carried by mosquito *Aedes aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus* can increase and 366 (91.5%) believed that increased mosquito borne disease and climatic change impact can be mitigated by improving housing.

Knowledge	Yes	No
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Is a matter of concern for you	355(88.8)	45(11.2)
Can increase disease carried by mosquito <i>Aedes aegypti</i> and <i>Ae. Albopictus</i>	361(90.2)	39(9.8)
Increase mosquito borne disease and climatic change impact can be mitigated by improving housing	366(91.5)	34(8.5)

Table 8: Knowledge About Climatic Change Link To Chikungunya Vector Proof Housing

5.11: Perception about practices regarding chikungunya vector proof housing

Among 400 respondents, 227 (56.8%) were strongly agreed that Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika disease are spread by Aedes mosquito species, 85 (21.2%) were agreed, 64 (16.0%) were undecided, 24 (6.0%) were disagreed and 0 (0.0%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 57 (14.2%) were strongly agreed that do not feel concerned about the presence of mosquitoes in their house, 18 (4.5%) were agreed, 54 (13.5%) were undecided, 158 (39.5%) were disagreed and 113 (28.2%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 208 (52.0%) were strongly agreed that they are susceptible to be infected with mosquito bite, 144 (36.0%) were agreed, 27 (6.8%) were undecided, 9 (2.2%) were disagreed and 12 (3.0%) were strongly disagreed.

Among respondents, 106 (26.5%) were strongly agreed that they do not consider mosquito prevention interventions as one of the important factor when constructing their house, 129 (32.2%) were agreed, 56 (14.0%) were undecided, 91 (22.8%) were disagreed and 18 (4.5%) were strongly disagreed.

Out of these respondents, 260 (65.0%) were strongly agreed that mosquitoes enter their house through open doors and windows, 115 (28.8%) were agreed, 11 (2.8%) were undecided, 5 (1.2%) were disagreed and 9 (2.2%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 215 (53.8%) were strongly agreed that it is possible that house design can prevent entry and breeding of mosquito, 83 (20.8%) were agreed, 30 (7.5%) were undecided, 67 (16.8%) were disagreed and 5 (1.2%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 190 (47.5%) were strongly agreed that as “Necessary Intervention” against mosquito they have screened windows and eaves so that their house becomes chikungunya vector proof, 155 (38.8%) were agreed, 19 (4.8%) were undecided, 19 (4.8%) were disagreed and 17 (4.2%) were strongly disagreed.

Out of 400 respondents, 250 (62.5%) were strongly agreed that they have well fitted the ceiling of their house to prevent mosquito entry, 131 (32.8%) were agreed, 15 (3.75%) were undecided, 3 (0.75%) were disagreed and 1 (0.25%) were strongly disagreed.

Result shows that among 400 respondents, 218 (54.5%) were strongly agreed that they frequently check that gutters in and around house are completely covered, 116 (29.0%) were agreed, 32 (8.0%) were undecided, 14 (3.5%) were disagreed and 20 (5.0%) were strongly disagreed.

Among respondents, 195 (48.8%) were strongly agreed that they do have time so that they dispose of rubbish regularly from their house, 148 (37.0%) were agreed, 39 (9.8%) were undecided, 13 (3.2%) were disagreed and 5 (1.2%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 254 (63.5%) were strongly agreed that removal of stagnant water from water infrastructure lid is necessary, 121 (30.2%) were agreed, 7 (1.8%) were undecided, 6 (1.5%) were disagreed and 12 (3.0%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 269 (67.2%) were strongly agreed that frequent emptying and cleaning of essential containers i.e. air cooler can prevent chikungunya disease, 97 (24.2%) were agreed, 27 (6.8%) were undecided, 0 (0.0%) were disagreed and 7 (1.8%) were strongly disagreed.

Among these respondents, 228 (57.0%) were strongly agreed that they have a reliable supply of piped water at their home, 124 (31.0%) were agreed, 27 (6.8%) were undecided, 7 (1.8%) were disagreed and 14 (3.5%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 212 (53.0%) were strongly agreed that their piped water supply had leaks and they have sealed them, 141 (35.2%) were agreed, 25 (6.2%) were undecided, 19 (4.8%) were disagreed and 3 (0.8%) were strongly disagreed.

Among 400 respondents, 188 (47.0%) were strongly agreed that they always check cracks and crevices in wall, floor and roof and cement them, 144 (36.0%)

were agreed, 32 (8.0%) were undecided, 17 (4.2%) were disagreed and 19(4.8%) were strongly disagreed.

Out of these respondents, 261 (65.2%) were strongly agreed that they completely cover water storage container, 135 (33.8%) were agreed, 4 (1.0%) were undecided, 0 (0.0%) were disagreed and 0 (0.0%) were strongly disagreed.

Among respondents, 215 (53.8%) were strongly agreed that environment surrounding house can influence mosquito density therefore house owners are responsible for mosquito management surrounding house, 136 (34.0%) were agreed, 15 (3.8%) were undecided, 34 (8.5%) were disagreed and 0 (0.0%) were strongly disagreed.

Out of 400 respondents, 208 (52.0%) were strongly agreed that mosquito management surrounding the house is the responsibility of government, 125 (31.2%) were agreed, 25 (6.2%) were undecided, 23 (5.8%) were disagreed and 19 (4.8%) were strongly disagreed.

Household Perceptions About Chikungunya Vector Proof Housing Practice	Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree
	N%	N%	N%	N%	N%
I think/ believe that Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika disease are spread by Aedes mosquito species.	227(56.8)	85(21.2)	64(16.0)	24(6.0)	0(0.0)
I think/believe that mosquitoes enter my house through open doors and windows.	260(65.0)	115(28.8)	11(2.8)	5(1.2)	9(2.2)
I do not feel concerned about the presence of mosquitoes in my house.	57(14.2)	18(4.5)	54(13.5)	158(39.5)	113(28.2)
I think/believe that I am susceptible to be infected with mosquito bite.	208(52.0)	144(36.0)	27(6.8)	9(2.2)	12(3.0)
We do not consider mosquito prevention interventions as one of the important factor when constructing our house.	106(26.5)	129(32.2)	56(14.0)	91(22.8)	18(4.5)
I think/believe, it is possible that house design can prevent entry and breeding of mosquito.	215(53.8)	83(20.8)	30(7.5)	67(16.8)	5(1.2)
I think/believe that as “Necessary Intervention” against mosquito I have screened windows and eaves so that my house becomes chikungunya vector proof.	190(47.5)	155(38.8)	19(4.8)	19(4.8)	17(4.2)
I have well fitted the ceiling of my house to prevent mosquito entry.	150(37.5)	131(32.8)	58(14.5)	56(14.0)	5(1.2)

We frequently check that gutters in and around house are completely covered.	218(54.5)	116(29.0)	32(8.0)	14(3.5)	20(5.0)
I do have time so that I dispose off rubbish regularly from my house.	195(48.8)	148(37.0)	39(9.8)	13(3.2)	5(1.2)
Removal of stagnant water from water infrastructure lid is necessary.	254(63.5)	121(30.2)	7(1.8)	6(1.5)	12(3.0)
Frequent emptying and cleaning of essential containers i.e. air cooler can prevent chikungunya disease.	269(67.2)	97(24.2)	27(6.8)	0(0.0)	7(1.8)
I have a reliable supply of piped water at my house.	228(57.0)	124(31.0)	27(6.8)	7(1.8)	14(3.5)
My piped water supply had leaks and I have sealed them.	212(53.0)	141(35.2)	25(6.2)	19(4.8)	3(0.8)
I always check cracks and crevices in wall, floor and roof and cement them.	188(47.0)	144(36.0)	32(8.0)	17(4.2)	19(4.8)
We completely cover water storage container.	261(65.2)	135(33.8)	4(1.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
The environment surrounding house can influence mosquito density therefore house owners are responsible for mosquito management surrounding house.	215(53.8)	136(34.0)	15(3.8)	34(8.5)	0(0.0)
Mosquito management surrounding the house is the responsibility of government.	208(52.0)	125(31.2)	25(6.2)	23(5.8)	19(4.8)

Table 9: Perception about practices regarding chikungunya vector proof housing

5.12: Chikunguniya Vector Proof Housing Practice Barriers

Among respondents, 188 (47.0%) were not owner of house, 294 (73.5%) had financial issues, 294 (73.5%) had lack of knowledge about preventive measures and 55 (13.8%) believed that screening may obstruct ventilation that could be perceived barriers related to chikungunya vector proof housing.

Barriers	Yes	No
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
House not owned	188(47.0)	212(53.0)
Financial issues	294(73.5)	106(26.5)
Lack of detail knowledge about mosquito preventive measures	294(73.5)	106(26.5)
Thinking that mosquito screening may obstruct ventilation	265(66.2)	345(86.2)

Table 10: Chikunguniya Vector Proof Housing Practice Barriers

**5.13: Health Education Regarding Chikungunya
Vector Proof Housing.**

Among 400 respondents, 327 (81.8%) believed that health education regarding mosquito proof housing in their area is necessary while 73 (18.2%) said no.

Among respondents, 276 (69.0%) believed that health authorities free brochure or online information is the most effective way of transmitting health information regarding chikungunya vector proof housing while 363 (90.8%), 292 (73.0%), 327 (81.8%), 297 (74.2%) and 242 (60.5%) respondents believed that health worker home visit, newspaper, television/radio, social media and community events, respectively.

Source of information	Yes	No
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Do you think/believe that health education regarding mosquito proof housing in your area is necessary?	327(81.8)	73(18.2)
Health authorities free brochure or online information	276(69.0)	124(31.0)
Health worker home visit	363(90.8)	37(9.2)
Newspaper	292(73.0)	108(27.0)
Television/radio	327(81.8)	73(18.2)
Social media	297(74.2)	103(25.8)
Community events	242(60.5)	158(39.5)

**Table 11: Health Education Regarding Chikungunya
Vector Proof Housing.**

CHAPTER 6

DISCUSSION

WHO document “Keeping the vector out” highlights the significance of vector proof house like a barrier against the vector borne diseases such as Chikungunya, Dengue and Zika. Keeping in view its guidelines present community based observational study was carried out about Community perceptions regarding Chikungunya vector proof housing in Lahore, Pakistan for sustainable development.

Sociodemographic data of the households revealed, that most of the respondents (69.0%) were upto 34 years old and remaining proportion (31.0%) was more than 34 years old. Among households, (53.5%) of the respondents were males while (46.5%) were females. A similar study carried out by Rashid and colleagues (2018) reported in their study that more than half (51.5%) of respondents were female and 48.5% were male respondents.⁷ while Dhaduk et al, (2013) demonstrated almost comparable results that majority (60.0%) of the respondents were upto 34 years old and 40.0% respondents were more than 34 years old.¹⁰⁸ Regarding family size of our study, most of the respondents had 3 children or more and majority had ≥ 5 family members in the house.

Vector Proof Housing study was conducted in an area of metropolitan city where major proportion (98.2%) of respondents were literate and (70.2%) respondents employed while only 1.8% were illiterate and 29.8% were unemployed The findings of study are comparable but exhibited better scenario than the study undertaken by Sharma and fellows (2017) who reported that majority of the respondents (91.0%) were literate and employed (58.9%) and only 9.0% respondents were illiterate and about 41.1% of respondents had no job.¹⁰⁹

Traditional house design in Lahore is a prominent feature of the local architectural style due to its prolonged association with historical context. Brick masonry has been used as construction method for about a century and it

still has maintained its reputation. Housing units are further divided into different categories depending on income and family size of the home owners. Studying the house design, its type, age of houses and ownership in town it was found that more than half of the respondents (53.0%) were owners and most of the houses (86.8%) were made of concrete, (13.2%) with mixed material bricked i.e (Brick masonry style and concrete material). Discussing the age of houses in town households reported, 17.5% were living in houses that were upto 4 years old, 12.8% were living in 5-8 years old houses and 69.7% respondents living in houses that were built 9 year before or more. A similar study undertaken by Kaindoa and coworkers (2018) asserted that 36.5% respondents were living in houses that were upto 4 years old, 26.5% were living in 5-8 years old houses and 37.0% respondents living in houses that were built 9 year before or more.¹¹⁰ Regarding housing type Dhaduk et al, (2013) studied that majority of the houses (96.7%) were made of concrete and 3.3% houses were made of mixed material.¹⁰⁸

“Climate change” one of the main Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), has emerged as a major threat for Pakistan and it is struggling to meet its challenges, so far the sector of health is concerned. Our study showed a positive concern (88.8%) regarding climate change and global warming because (90.2%) believed that it can increase disease carried by mosquito *Aedes aegypti* & *Ae. albopictus* which are responsible for the spread of Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika as reported by (56.8% who strongly agreed) and (21.2% agreed). The results of study exhibited better scenario than the study performed by Rashid et al, (2018) who elucidated that 50.2% respondents believed that Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika disease are spread by *Aedes* mosquito species.⁷ Furthermore, (67.7%) of our households had concern about the presence of mosquitoes in their house and they believed that they are susceptible to be infected with mosquito bite.

The WHO Department of Public Health, Environmental and Social Determinants of Health are developing guidelines regarding Vector proof houses, against vector borne disease and climatic change. This sector carries immense importance as WHO and the Roll Back Malaria initiative has considered it as centre to the multisectoral response required to reduce vector-borne diseases. In our Study

(91.5%) households believe that Increase mosquito borne disease and climatic change impact can be mitigated by improving housing and (95.4%) believed that, it is possible that house design can prevent entry and breeding of mosquito but only (27.3%) consider mosquito prevention interventions as one of the important factor when constructing their house. Here it seems, that most of the people have concept of improving housing, but they not considering mosquito vector proof practices as an important intervention while constructing their houses may be due to lack of complete knowledge about preventive interventions as mentioned by (73.5%) of the households, or they could not afford modern building materials as (73.5%) also reported financial issues. However, (13.8%) households did not screened their house considering mosquito screen as a barrier which obstructs ventilation. In study done by Kaindoa and coworkers (2018), researcher explored that 58.5% respondents considered mosquito prevention interventions as a significant factor when constructing their house.¹¹⁰The findings of our research indicated that financial issues, lacking ownership and insufficient knowledge are the leading factors that affected vector proof housing practice. These were the associated barriers that disrupted chikungunya vector proof housing. A study carried out by Kaindoa and coworkers (2018) demonstrated that financial issues were the major problem among respondents and they were compelled to reside in the poorly constructed homes which had gaps on walls, eaves and doors.¹⁰ Here it is important for Health organizations or Government to revise the building codes, and create institutions of vocational training, who teach the necessary skills to enable homeowners, local businesses and architects to deliver the interventions, keeping in view the cost benefit of project and solution to the adverse effects of screening such as reduction of indoor ventilation. This not only helps to reduce the costs of interventions, but it involves and sensitizes the community while strengthens the local economy.

A crucial element in prevention of vector-borne diseases is behavioral change. Health education can improve awareness among people; so that they know how to protect themselves and their communities from mosquitoes, but it doesnot promise their behavior change. In our study (93.8%) respondents were aware that mosquitoes enter their house through open doors and windows, and mainstream of the respondents adopted preventive practices such as (86.3%) respondents

believed that as “Necessary Intervention” against mosquito they have screened windows and eaves so that their home becomes chikungunya vector proof, (95.3%) respondents well fitted the ceiling of their house to avoid mosquito entry. A large number of respondents had repaired leaks in their piped water supply and sealed them up, (83.0%) always checked cracks and crevices in the wall, floor and roof and cemented them and (99.0%) completely covered water storage container. Continue to study mosquito breeding preventive measures measures taken by households. It is worth noting that most participants often checked that gutters in and around their home were completely covered, about (85.8%) of the households had time to dispose off rubbish from their house, (93.7%) of respondents believed that removal of stagnant water from water infrastructure lid is necessary and (91.4%) of the respondents were aware that frequent emptying and cleaning of essential containers such as air cooler can prevent chikungunya disease. A study carried out by Kaindoa and coworkers (2018) showed quite similar results that 61.5% respondents employed strategies such as netting on window, blocking eaves, using bricks on wall, using cement on wall to make their homes vector proof.¹¹⁰In another study Sharma and fellows (2017) also demonstrated quite similar results but only 25.7% of the households had time to dispose off garbage regularly from their house.¹⁰⁹

Despite of adopting most of the preventive measures against mosquito, (81.8%) households desired that health education regarding chikunguniya mosquito proof housing is necessary in their area, this shows that community was previously sensitized by Dangué and Malaria disease therefore they adopted preventive practices, But still they need to know and get detail knowledge about Chikunguniya vector proof housing interventions. As in our study (16.0% of the households were undecided and 6.0% disagreed) regarding their believethat”Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika disease are spread by Aedes mosquito species.”

Health communication and education is an art requires combined efforts of mass media and health personal having knowledge about the principles of health promotion or behavioral change for changes in behavior and not just for changes in knowledge or attitudes.

In our study of households, we found that majority of respondents had concept of changing house design and its impact on their protection against climatic change and vector borne diseases but due to lack of detail knowledge and other multiple reasons they were not adopting some of the mosquito proof interventions. Therefore, they urged the need of health communication channel for appropriate knowledge regarding chikunguniya vector proof housing. Among the respondents, (90.8%) believed that most effective way of transmitting health information regarding chikungunya vector proof housing is health worker home visit, followed by television/radio (81.8%), social media (74.2%), newspaper (73.0%), online information and free brochure from health authorities (69.0%) and community events (60.5%). A study carried out in 2018 by Rashid and colleagues reported that effective mode of communication among (23.2%) respondents was social media, followed by television (21.0%), newspaper (14.6%), family members/friends (12.6%), school teachers (12.4%), doctors (9.5%) and radio (6.0%) while (0.5%) respondents had no knowledge.⁷ Another similar study performed by Sharma and fellows (2017) highlighted that among (68.6) respondents major source of information was television, followed by newspaper/magazine (46.7%), doctor (33.9%), friends and relatives (23.4%), health department staff (22.7%), hoarding/banners (18.7%), radio (18.5%) and advertisement/ pamphlets (9.5%).¹⁰⁹

This shows a progressive change in the trend of society getting more inclined towards the use of electronic media and lady sanitary patrol home visit. As communication specialist on mass media is not an epidemiologist. Therefore, there is need for epidemiologists and medical personnel on mass media to address accurate and useful information with the broader community through the media for behavior change and to reduce the chance of misinterpretation or sensationalization of information.

Also, Information, education and communication (IEC) programmes may need to be reviewed to allow health workers to maximize opportunities for community education.

Intervention in the construction of vector-protected residential buildings without environmental control is of no importance, and in our study there has already been a very high level of awareness of how the characteristics of residential buildings

and the environment can affect the density of mosquitoes. As about (87.8% of households, strongly agreed and agreed) that environment surrounding house can influence mosquito density therefore they themselves are responsible for mosquito management surrounding the house, while (83.2% of the respondents, also strongly agreed and agreed) that mosquito management surrounding the house is the responsibility of government, or can be said to believe that the government and families are equally responsible for maintaining a clean environment around the house. A similar study carried out by Alobuia et al, (2015) showed quite similar behavior exhibited by (54.7 %) households who believed that both government and households are responsible for maintaining the vector proof environment outside the houses.¹¹⁶ In our study, such results are primarily because the population was mostly educated belonging to urban background already sensitized by Malaria and Dangué disease, if the similar study was conducted at an area having rural background or unsensitized population, we may have found different results.

CHAPTER 7

7.1 CONCLUSION

Efforts are being made to develop vaccines against Chikungunya, Zika and Dengue but still any effective treatment is not available. Therefore, preventing or reducing transmission depends completely upon mosquito vectors control or interruption of human vector contact. Present study assessed the community perceptions regarding chikungunya vector proof housing in Lahore for sustainable development. Study concluded that significant majority of the respondents believed that climatic change and global warming increase the chikungunya disease carried by mosquito *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes Albopictus* and its impact can be mitigated by vector proof housing, but practice of vector proof housing intervention was given less priority by respondents when it came to house construction. Health program planner need to identify and facilitate removal of barriers such as households financial issues, lack of detail information about vector proof house and cost benefit of project for behavior change. Further studies are needed on large scale to assess the value of vector proof housing structure in context of vector borne disease prevention.

7.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

- Health organizations or Government must revise the building codes and create institutions of vocational training who teach the necessary skills to enable homeowners, local businesses and architects to deliver the interventions like screening windows, doors and eaves of houses, fitting ceilings, filling the cracks and crevices in walls, floors and roofs, installing reliable supply of piped water, adequate sanitary facilities etc. Keeping in view the cost benefit of project and solution to the adverse effects of screening such as reduction of indoor ventilation. A proper designed house can prevent mosquito entry as well as breeding within house. This not only helps to reduce the costs of interventions, but it involves and sensitizes the community while strengthens the local economy.
- Information, education and communication (IEC) intervention programmes may need to be reviewed to ensure that health professionals are able to maximize opportunities for educating the public.
- There is need for epidemiologists and medical personnel on mass media to address accurate and useful information with the broader community through the media for behavior change regarding mosquito proof housing and vector control this will reduce the chance of misinterpretation or sensationalization of information.
- As *Aedes aegypti* is a day biting mosquito. It means that the mosquito is most active during daylight, for approximately two hours after sunrise and several hours before sunset. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct such research in offices, markets and institutes to educate community regarding their safety, so that employees who left for work early can stay safe.
- Health community events are effective mode of health communication channel. If properly organized, can be the best source of health education and behavior change.

7.3 LIMITATIONS

The following limitations were recognized in the course of this study.

- This study was conducted in only one town of Lahore.
- Due to time constraints, a sample of 400 respondents was included in the study.
- Focus group discussions and In-depth interviews can further explore social problems associated with vector proof housing. Involving health professionals and architects can be of great value in such context.
- Housing interventional experimental research is needed in Pakistan to fully explore the benefits of vector-protected housing.

CHAPTER 8

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CHAPTER 9

ANNEXURES 9.1:

9.1.1 CONSENT FORM

You are invited to participate in a research study conducted by Serena Taj. The purpose of this research is to evaluate the “Community Perceptions Regarding Chikungunya Vector Proof Housing In Lahore, Pakistan For Sustainable Development.”

Risks and Discomforts

There will be no known risks associated with this research.

Potential Benefits

There will be benefits to the participant that would result from their participation in this research.

Protection of Confidentiality

Measures will be taken to protect the privacy. The identity will not be revealed in any publication resulting from this study.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research study is voluntary. You may choose not to participate and you may withdraw your consent to participate any time. You will not be penalized in any way should you decide not you participate or to withdraw from this study.

CONSENT

I have read this consent form and have been given the opportunity to ask questions. I give my consent to participate in this study.

Participant’s Signature _____ Date: _____

A copy of this consent form should be given to the participant

عنوان: لاہور پاکستان میں پابدار ترقی کے حصول کیلئے چکنگنیا مچھر پروف گھر کے متعلق گروہ تحقیق میں شرکت کا دعوت نامہ شمولیت

کے خیالات کا مطالعہ

نقصانات اور تکلیف: اس تحقیق سے کسی قسم کے نقصان یا تکلیف کا اندیشہ نہیں ہے۔

ممکنہ فوائد: آپکو ایک اہم تحقیق میں حصہ لینے کا موقعہ دیا جائے گا۔

رازداری کا تحفظ: ہم آپ کی معلومات کے تحفظ کے لیے وہ سب کچھ کریں گے جو ہم کر سکتے ہیں۔ تحقیق کے متعلق اکتھپی کی گئی تمام معلومات کو انتہائی خفیہ رکھا جائے گا۔ ڈیٹا انٹری اور تجزیے کے دوران آپ کے متعلق وہ تمام معلومات جن سے آپ کی شناخت ہو سکتی ہو کو ختم کر دیا جائے گا۔ اس تحقیق کے نتیجے میں شائع ہونے والی کسی بھی اشاعت میں آپ کی شناخت کو ظاہر نہیں کیا جائے گا۔

رضاکارانہ شمولیت: اس تحقیقی مطالعہ میں آپ کی شرکت رضاکارانہ ہے۔ آپ کو شرکت نہ کرنے اور کسی بھی وقت بغیر وجہ بتانے اس تحقیق میں شمولیت کو چھوڑنے کا اختیار ہے۔ شرکت نہ کرنے یا اس میں شمولیت کو

چھوڑنے کی صورت میں آپ کے خلاف کوئی کارروائی نہیں کی جائے گی

درج ذیل معلومات تحقیق میں شامل ہونے والوں کے لیے پڑھنا اور انکا جواب دینے کے لیے خانہ نمیندرج کریں

میں نے معلوماتی شیٹ جو کہ تحقیق کی وضاحت کر رہی ہے کو سمجھ لیا ہے اور مجھے تحقیق کے □
سوالات کرنے کا موقع دیا گیا تھا۔

میں سمجھ گیا/گی ہوں کہ میری شرکت رضاکارانہ ہے اور یہ کہ میں کسی بھی وقت اپنا ارادہ بدل □
سکتا/سکتی ہوں اور تحقیق سے دستبردار ہو سکتا/سکتی

میں سمجھ گیا/گی ہوں کہ میرے جوابات خفیہ رکھے جائیں گے۔ میں محققین کو اس بات کی اجازت □
دینا/دیتی ہوں کہ وہ جوابات کو جانچ سکیں۔

میں سمجھ گیا/گی ہوں کہ معلومات میرے نام کے بجائے نمبر کی صورت میں محفوظ کی جائیں گی۔ تا □
کہ میں نتائج کی اشاعت کے دوران کسی بھی طرح سے شناخت نہ کیا جا سکوں۔ میں اس بات سے رضامند ہوں کہ جو معلومات مجھ سے لی جائیں گی وہ تحقیق میں استعمال ہوں گی۔

میں اوپر بتائی گئی تحقیق میں شامل ہونے کے لیے رضامند ہوں اور محققین کو اپنا پتہ تبدیل ہونے کی □
صورت میں مطلع کروں گا/گی۔

رضا مندی: میں نے یہ اجازت نامہ پڑھا ہے اور مجھے سوال پوچھنے کا موقع دیا گیا ہے۔ میں اس سٹیڈی میں شرکت کے راضی ہوں۔

شرکت کنندہ کا نام _____ دستخط _____ تاریخ _____
اجازت لینے والے کا نام _____ دستخط _____ تاریخ _____
اس اجازت نامہ کی ایک نقل آپکو دی جانی چاہے۔

9.2 QUESTIONNAIRE

“COMMUNITY PERCEPTIONS REGARDING CHIKUNGUNYA VECTOR PROOF HOUSING IN LAHORE, PAKISTAN FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT”

S.#	QUESTION ASKED
I. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION OF RESPONDENT	
1.	Name:
2.	Address:
3.	Age: A: 18-34 <input type="checkbox"/> B: 35-49 <input type="checkbox"/> C: 50-64 <input type="checkbox"/> D: 65 and older <input type="checkbox"/>
4.	Sex : A: Male <input type="checkbox"/> B: Female <input type="checkbox"/>
5.	Education: A. None <input type="checkbox"/> B. Primary <input type="checkbox"/> C. Secondary <input type="checkbox"/> D. University <input type="checkbox"/> E. Technical <input type="checkbox"/>
6.	House ownership: A. Owner <input type="checkbox"/> B. Tenant <input type="checkbox"/>
7.	Housing Type: A. Concrete <input type="checkbox"/> B. Bricked <input type="checkbox"/> Mix <input type="checkbox"/>
8.	Employment: A. Employed <input type="checkbox"/> B. Unemployed <input type="checkbox"/>
9.	Children: A. None <input type="checkbox"/> B. 1-2 <input type="checkbox"/> C. ≥ 3 <input type="checkbox"/>
10.	Total in household A. 1-4 <input type="checkbox"/> B. ≥ 5 <input type="checkbox"/>
11.	Age of House (date of construction) A. < 4 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> B. 5-8 years ago <input type="checkbox"/> C. > 9 years ago <input type="checkbox"/>

**II. KNOWLEDGE ABOUT CLIMATIC CHANGE LINK TO CHIKUNGUNYA
MOSQUITO PROOF HOUSING**

S.#	QUESTION ASKED	YES	NO
12.	Do you think/ believe that climatic change and global warming?		
	A. Is a matter of concern for you?		
	B. Can increase disease carried by mosquito Aedes aegypti and Ae. Albopictus?		
	C. Increase mosquito borne disease and climatic change impact can be mitigated by improving housing?		

111. PERCEPTION ABOUT PRACTICES REGARDING CHIKUNGUNYA VECTOR PROOF HOUSING.

Do you think/believe that you have adopted following protective measures as “Necessary Intervention” against mosquito; to make your house chikungunya vector proof?

S.#	QUESTION ASKED (LIKERT SCALE ADAPTED)*	SA	A	UD	D	SD
13	I think/believe that Dengue, Chikungunya and Zika disease are spread by Aedes mosquito species?					
14	I do not feel concerned about the presence of mosquitoes in my house.					
15	I think/believe that I am susceptible to be infected with mosquito bite					
16.	We do not consider mosquito prevention interventions as one of the important factor when constructing our house.					
17	I think/believe that mosquitoes enter my house through open doors and windows.					
18.	I think/believe, it is possible that house design can prevent entry and breeding of mosquito.					
19.	I think/believe that as “Necessary Intervention” against mosquito I have screened windows and eaves so that my house becomes chikungunya vector proof.					
20.	I have well fitted the ceiling of my house to prevent mosquito entry.					
21.	We frequently check that gutters in and around house are completely covered.					
22.	I do have time so that I dispose of rubbish regularly from my house.					
23.	Removal of stagnant water from water infrastructure lid is necessary.					
24.	Frequent emptying and cleaning of essential containers i.e. air cooler can prevent chikungunya disease.					
25.	I have a reliable supply of piped water at my home					
26.	My piped water supply had leaks and I have sealed them.					
27.	I always check cracks and crevices in wall, floor and roof and cement them.					
28.	We completely cover water storage container.					
29.	The environment surrounding house can influence mosquito density therefore house owners are responsible for mosquito management surrounding house.					
30.	Mosquito management surrounding the house is the responsibility of government.					

SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, UN=Undecided, D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree

IV. PERCEIVED BARRIERS RELATED TO CHIKUNGUNYA VECTOR PROOF HOUSING

S.#	QUESTION ASKED	YES	NO
31.	If you have not adopted some of the above mentioned (III) protective measures against mosquito at your house following could be the reasons in your opinion?		
	A. House not owned.		
	B. Financial Issues.		
	C Lack of detail knowledge about mosquito preventive measures..		
	D. Thinking that mosquito screen may obstruct ventilation.		

V. SOURCE OF INFORMATION REGARDING CHIKUNGUNYA VECTOR PROOF HOUSING

S.#	QUESTION ASKED	YES	NO
32	Do you think/believe that health education regarding mosquito proof housing in your area is necessary?		
33.	What do you think/believe is the most effective way of transmitting health information regarding Chikungunya vector proof housing?		
	A. Health Authorities free brochure or online information		
	B.Health worker home visit.		
	C. News paper.		
	D. Television/Radio.		
	E. Social Media.		
	F. Community events.		

Signature of Respondent: _____

تحقیق میں شرکت کا دعوت نامہ شمولیت کے عنوان: لاہور پاکستان میں پابیدار ترقی کے حصول کیلئے چکنگنیا مچھر پروف گھر کے متعلق گروہ خیالات کا مطالعہ۔
نقصانات اور تکلیف: اس تحقیق سے کسی قسم کے نقصان یا تکلیف کا اندیشہ نہیں ہے۔
ممکنہ فوائد: آپکو ایک اہم تحقیق میں حصہ لینے کا موقعہ دیا جائے گا

نمبر شمار	پوچھے جانے والے سوال
1	آپ کا نام :
2	آپ کا پتہ:
3	آپ کی عمر: □ د- 65 سے زیادہ □ ج-50-64 □ ب-35-49 □ الف-18-34
4	□ (ب) عورت) □ (ا) مرد جنس:
5	□ (خ) فنی □ (ج) اعلیٰ تعلیم □ (د) انٹرمیڈیٹ □ (ب) پرائمری □ آپ کی تعلیم: (ا) ناخواندہ □ تعلیم
6	رہائشی حیثیت: □ (ب) کرائے دار □ (ا) مالک مکان)
7	آپ کے گھر کی ساخت: □ (ج) کچا پکا مکان) □ (ب) کچا مکان) □ (ا) پکا مکان)
8	ملازمت: □ (ب) بے روزگار □ (ا) ملازم
9	گھر میں بچوں کی تعداد: □ ≥ (د) 3 □ (ب) 1-2 □ (ا) کوئی نہیں
10	گھر کے کل افراد کی تعداد: □ ≥ (ب) 5 □ (ا) 1-4
11	گھر کی تعمیر کی تاریخ: □ (ج) > 9 سال قبل □ (ب) 5-8 سال قبل □ (ا) > 4 سال)

موسمی تبدیلی سے مچھر پروف گھر کے تعلق کے متعلق معلومات : آپ کے خیالات			
نمبر شمار	پوچھے جانے والے سوال	ہاں	نہیں
12	کیا آپ کو لگتا ہے / یقین ہے کہ موسمی تبدیلی اور عالمی حرارت (گلوبل وارمنگ)؟		
	(ا) آپ کے لیے باعثِ فکر ہے۔		
	(ب) مچھر ایڈیز کے ذریعے پھیلنے والی بیماری میں اضافہ کر سکتی ہے۔		
	(ج) رہائش بہتر بنانے کے ذریعے مچھروں سے بڑھتے ہوئے امراض اور موسمی تبدیلی کے اثر کو کم کیا جاسکتا ہے۔		

چکنگونیا مچھر پروف گھر کے طرز عمل کو اپنانے کے بارے میں آپ کے خیالات III-					
کیا آپ کو لگتا ہے / یقین ہے کہ آپ نے مچھر کے خلاف "ضروری مداخلت" کے بطور مندرجہ ذیل حفاظتی اقدامات اپنانے میں تاکہ آپ کا گھر چکنگونیا مچھر پروف بن سکے؟					
نمبر	پوچھے جانے والے سوال	مکمل متفق	متفق	غیر یقین	متفق نہیں
13	مجھے لگتا ہے / یقین ہے کہ ڈینگی، چکنگونیا اور ڈیکا بیماری (ایڈیز مچھر) کے ذریعے پھیلتی ہے۔				
14	مجھے اپنے گھر میں مچھروں کی موجودگی کی فکر نہیں ہے۔				
15	مجھے لگتا ہے / یقین ہے کہ مجھ کو مچھر کے کاٹنے سے متاثر ہونے کا خدشہ ہے۔				
16	ہم اپنے گھر کی تعمیر کرتے وقت مچھروں کی روک تھام کے اقدامات کو ایک غیر ضروری عنصر سمجھتے ہیں۔				
17	مجھے لگتا ہے / یقین ہے کہ کھلے دروازوں اور کھڑکیوں کے ذریعے مچھر میرے گھر میں داخل ہوتے ہیں۔				
18	مجھے لگتا ہے / یقین ہے، کہ یہ ممکن ہے گھر کا تعمیری ڈیزائن مچھر کے داخلے اور اس کی افزائش کو روک سکتا ہے۔				
19	مجھے لگتا ہے / یقین ہے، کہ میں نے مچھر کے خلاف (Eave space) "ضروری مداخلت" کے بطور کھڑکی اور چھجہ کے خلا پہ مچھر پروف جالی نصب کی ہے تاکہ میرا گھر (space) چکنگونیا مچھر پروف بن سکے۔				
20	مجھے لگتا ہے / یقین ہے، کہ میں نے چھت مکمل نصب کی ہے تاکہ مچھر میرے گھر میں داخل نہ ہوں۔				
21	ہم اکثر یہ چیک کرتے ہیں کہ گھر کے اندرونی اور بیرونی نالے (گٹر) مکمل طور پر ڈھکے ہونے ہیں۔				
22	میرے پاس وقت ہے تاکہ میں اپنے گھر سے مستقل طور پر کوڑے کو ٹھکانے لگاؤں۔				
23	پانی کے ذخائر کے ڈھکن سے جمع شدہ پانی کا اخراج ضروری ہے۔				
24	ضروری کنٹینر جیسا کہ اینر کولر کی بار بار صفائی اور خالی کرنے کے ذریعے چکنگونیا بیماری سے بچا سکتا ہے۔				

					25	مجھے لگتا ہے / یقین ہے ، کہ میرے گھر میں پائپ کے ذریعے پانی کی قابل اعتماد فراہمی ہے۔
					26	پائپ کے شکاف سے پانی کے رساؤ کی روک تھام کے لئے میں نے اقدامات کیے ہیں۔
					27	میں ہمیشہ دیوار، فرش اور چھت کی دراڑوں کی جانچ کرتا ہوں اور ان کو سیمنٹ کرتا ہوں۔
					28	ہم پانی ذخیرہ کرنے والے کنٹینر کو مکمل طور پر ڈھانپتے ہیں۔
					29	گھر کے آس پاس کا ماحول مچھر کی کثافت کو متاثر کر سکتا ہے، اس لیے گھر کے آس پاس مچھروں کی روک تھام کے انتظام کے لئے گھر والے خود ذمہ دار ہیں۔
					30	گھر کے آس پاس مچھروں کی روک تھام کا انتظام، حکومت کی ذمہ داری ہے۔

چکنگونیا مچھر پروف گھر کے طرز عمل کونہ اپنانے کی سمجھی وجوہات-IV			
نمبر شمار	پوچھے جانے والے سوال	ہاں	نہیں
31	مچھر پروف حفاظتی اقدامات کو نہیں (III) اگر آپ نے اپنے گھر میں مذکورہ بالا اپنایا، تو آپ کی رائے کے مطابق کیا وجوہات ہو سکتی ہیں؟		
	مکان کی ملکیت نہیں ہے۔ (ا)		
	مالی مسائل۔ (ب)		
	مذکورہ بالا طریق کار کے بارے میں معلومات کا فقدان۔ (د)		
	مچھر پروف جالی ہوا کے گزر میں رکاوٹ بن سکتی ہے۔ (ج)		

چکنگونیا مچھر پروف گھر سے متعلق صحت کی تعلیم کا حصول : آپ کے خیالات V -			
نمبر شمار	پوچھے جانے والے سوال	ہاں	نہیں
32	کیا آپ کو لگتا ہے / یقین ہے کہ آپ کے علاقے میں چکنگونیا مچھر پروف گھر سے متعلق صحت کی تعلیم ضروری ہے؟		
33	آپ کے خیال کے مطابق چکنگونیا مچھر پروف گھر سے متعلق معلومات کی ترسیل کا کون سا ذریعہ موثر ہے؟		
	(ا) صحت اتھارٹی کا مفت بروشر یا آن لائن معلومات		
	(ب) صحت سے متعلق کارکن کا دورہ گھر		
	(ج) اخبار		
	(د) ٹی وی / ریڈیو		
	(ح) سوشل میڈیا، فیس بک وغیرہ		
	(خ) برادری میں صحت کی تقریبات		

جوابدہندگان کے دستخط:

9.3 POPULATION OF AZIZ BHATTI TOWN ACCORDING TO THE DOCUMENT PROVIDED BY DISTRICT HEALTH DEPARTMENT AZIZBHATTI TOWN LAHORE ON JULY 2019 IS 705311

**POPULATION OF AZIZ BHATTI TOWN, LAHORE
705311**

SR NO.	UC NAME
1	41 Harbanspura
2	43 Rasheed Pura
3	44 Fateh Garh
4	45 Nabi Pura
5	48 Mughal Pura
6	54 Mian Mir
7	55 Mustafabad
8	56 Ghazi Abad
9	57 Taj Bagh
10	58 Taj Pura
11	59 Al-Faisal Town
12	60 Guldashat Town
13	61 Bhangali

9.4 MAP OF 13 UNION COUNCILS, AZIZ BHATTI TOWN ON JULY 2019

9.5 DIFFERENT TYPE OF HOUSES; AZIZ BHATTI TOWN, LAHORE.

9.5.1 MOSQUITO SCREENED CONCRETE HOUSES, AMEERUDDIN PARK TAJPURA BAZAR, AZIZ BHATTI TOWN, LAHORE.

**9.5.2 HOUSE WITHOUT MOSQUITO SCREEN
GULZAIB SHAHEED ROAD.**

**9.5.3 WELL SCREENED HOUSES WITHOUT
SURROUNDING ENVIRONMENTAL CONTROL AZIZ BHATTI TOWN**

9.6 RANDOM LIST OF HOUSEHOLD AIZ BHATTI TOWN, LAHORE.

71979	Head Master	St # 16,H # 6,Bilal Park	55
23908	M.Shoukat	St # 48,H # 13	48
30160	Akhtar	St # 3,H # 17,Chaman Park	44
84684	Zeeshan	St #12,H # 3,Altaf Colony	44
22434	Ramzan	St # 21,H # 18,Androon Choubacha	60
34581	Mushtaq	St # 3,H # 18,Ghazi Peer Darbar	44
71421	Ishaq	St # 3,H # 2,Fiaz Park	44
98862	Riaz	St # 1,Rajbah Road Darogawala	41
16540	M.Afzal	Govt Tanderd Children Primery School St # 6,Mustafabad	54
52264	Ahsan Pean	H # 46,Androon Choubacha	55
18371	Noor Muhammad	St # 3,H # 10,Ghazi Peer Darbar	55
120051	M.Nafees	St # 4,H # 1,Saraye Roshan Deen	55
54296	Tahir	St # 5,H # 2,Dispencery Road	58
113598	Akhter	St # 6,Ahata Makhan Singh	48
110293	Naseer	St # 1,H # 15,Madina Colony	57
46928	Zulfaqar	St # 1,H # 18/1,Amertasri Mohallah	41
135702	arshad	St # 14,H # 14,Hameed Pura	45
43980	Tahir	St # 14/1/A,H # 4,Khajoor Wali Scheme	58
6582	Hamad Niaz	St # 15,H # 495 B	43
17455	Ishrat Riaz	H # 1/26,Suk Nehar Lal Pul	55
86157	Haji Javaid	H # 116,Shamshan Bhoomi Mustafabad	48
18013	Aslam	H # 150,A Block Tajpura	55
47843	M.Arshad	H # 5,Block 64 Railway Quarter	57
31633	Ishrat Riaz	H#12 St#13 Daira Prk Hameedpura	55
80263	Haji Javaid	H#17 st#105 Iltaf colony	48
72337	Aslam	H#44 St#35	55
132755	M.Arshad	Muslim Abad Main Railway Line	57
52822	Zahoor	St # 3,H # 2,Razzaq Colony	55
118019	Aleem Sarwar	St # 1,H # 3,Sagar Road Main Bazar	48
97031	Ateeq U Rehman	St # 1,Tajpura	60
86715	Liaqat	St # 12,H # 16,Amir Town	57
117661	M. Naveed	St # 2,H # 26,Iftikhar Park Mohallah Bagh	59
24823	Touqeer Butt	St # 20,H # 242,Rasheedpura	59
64053	Amjad	St # 26,H # 66,Muslim Abad	55
120966	Arshad	St # 3,H # 1,Zubair Block Dogaich	55
88189	Nazar	St # 4,H # 24,Choungi Gujjar Pura	43
113241	Irfan	St # 45,Ahata 204	54
38086	Abdurazzaq	St # 45/B,H # 1,Bhangali Mohallah	54
24265	Sadiq Younas	St # 48,H # 5,Mustafabad	57
102367	Shahid Mahmood	St # 5,H # 33,Altaf Colony	54
107346	Ayoob Ali	St # 6,Mehar Fiaz Colony	55
55769	Ahmed Deen	St # 7,H # 4,Nazmabad	56
109177	M.Husnain	St # 9,H # 4,Al-Madina Colony	55
123556	Ameer Ali	St # 9,H #4,Nazmabad	55
7140	M.Anees	St # 9,H# 8,Bhatta Chabeel	55
117103	Kahlid	St #14,H# 9,D Block Al Faisal Town	54
63138	Shabir	St #36,H # 17,Muslim Abad	41

87073	Dil Shad	St #50,H # 141,Mojahidabad	45
88547	Shehraz	St #8,H # 13,Ishwar Nagar	56
84126	Bilawal	St#12 H#53 Gulshan Park	44
97388	Ishfaq	St33 H#6 Faisal Park	44
20961	Saqlain Ali	St #10,H # 33,Shahid Park	55
39002	Khalid Iqbal	St # 8,H # 10,Ittihad Town	55
58159	Jaffar Abbas	St # 4,H # 24,Razzaq Colony	55
688	Zeeshan	Al Faisal Town	60
35139	Wali Muhammad	Al Faisal Town D Block	59
33107	Zahid	H # 105A ,Khurram Block	54
75842	Asif	H # 14 Ibraheem Colony	59
85599	Asmat	H # 2,Bilal Park	43
92967	Rafique	H # 29 ST # 4 Nizamabad	58
70863	Ali Akbar	H # 37,Ismail Town	55
137176	Waqar Ahmed	H # 38,Dargah Street 53	55
39560	Abdusattar	H # 4,Railway Quarter Muslim Abad	45
19845	Javaid Iqbal	H # 5,Block 62 Railway Quarter	57
115630	Zeeshan	H # 7,Railway Quarters	60
67558	Wali Muhammad	H # 70,Nagina House	59
73810	Zahid	H#14 St#14B	54
128334	Asif	H#28 St#21 Andron Chubacha	59
66085	Asmat	Hanif Park Madrassah Wali Gali	43
78231	Rafique	Main Road Janazgah Ganda Nala Ghosia Colony	58
115072	Javaid Iqbal	Muslim Abad Main Line	57
105872	Ali Akbar	Razzaq Colony Main Bazar	55
60190	Waqar Ahmed	Razzaq Colony St # 1,H # 7	55
95915	Abdusattar	Saraye Lal Singh 36	45
25382	Nayamat	St # 1, H # 16,Ghazi Peer	48
25739	Abdul Sattar	St # 1,H # 13,Amer Tarsi Mohallah	60
97946	Amjad	St # 1,H #22,Riaz Pura	45
120609	Sadique	St # 1/A,H # 1,Habib Park	59
15982	Yaseen	St # 10,H # 23,Gulshan Park	54
90578	Iqbal	St # 11,H # 12,Main Pakora Stop Ghaziabad	58
4751	Waqas	St # 13,H # 3,Nabi Nagar	55
87631	Ghulam Muhammad	St # 14,H # 5,Al-Madina Colony	43
13593	Ameer Ahmad	St # 14,H # 6,Gunj Mughalpura	60
61106	Rizwan	St # 18,H # 8,Faisal Park	55
129808	Ataullah	St # 19,Kothi Sarool Singh	59
61664	M.Shakeel	St # 2,H # 1,Canal Bank Road	55
91494	Javaid	St # 2,H # 22, Ghazi Peer	55
75284	Arif	St # 2,H # 4,Sunny Park	44
123913	Irfan	St # 20,H # 25,Javaid Colony	59
79347	Yasin	St # 20,H # 6,D Block	57
1804	Liaqat	St # 20,H # 7,D Block	55
96473	Khalid Bashir	St # 20,H #6,Amir Town	54
125029	M.Kamran	St # 22,Barkat Colony Rajbah Road	48
2719	Shafiullah	St # 22,H # 9,Mian Colony	59
130366	Javaid	St # 24,H # 27,Husnabad	54
23350	Hameed	St # 24,H # 28,Husnabad	54
68474	Ateeq	St # 26,H #515,Gulistan Colony Mustafabad	54

107704	Farhan	St # 26,H #515,Gulistan Colony Mustafabad	54
127977	Raza	St # 3,H # 2/A,Gunj Bazar	60
131839	Saleem	St # 3,H # 3,Bilal Park	58
18929	Saleem	St # 3,H # 9,Noor Colony	57
81736	Abbas	St # 30,H # 46,Usman Block Choungi Gujjar Pura	60
67916	Manzoor	St # 30/1,H # 1,Mian Colony	60
8056	M.Zubair	St # 32,H # 38	44
13035	Qayoom	St # 35,H # 18	60
99420	Aqib	St # 4,H # 68,Shoukat Hotal	54
116188	Ashiq	St # 4,Noori Darbar Road	59
29244	Taimoor	St # 4,Rehmat Colony	59
50791	Shakeel	St # 40,H #555,Gunj Bazar	55
22792	Nadeem Abbas	St # 42,H # 6,Maqbool Park	60
106788	Abbas	St # 45b,Madina Mohallah	58
94084	Irfan	St # 47,Muslim Mohallah	59
95557	M.Afzal	St # 5,H # 26,Mian Park	55
91136	Arif	St # 5,H # 4 A Block Al Faisal Town	44
104399	Imran	St # 5,Qlandarpura	60
64611	Makhan	St # 5/3,H # 10/5,Tariq Colony	60
82652	Waseem Abbas	St # 52,H # 13a,Mujahidabad	55
101809	Saqlain	St # 52,H # 9,Mustafabad	54
7698	Riaz	St # 53,H # 22/4,Mian Meer	55
78789	Ataullah	St # 5a,H # 7,Gunj Bazar	59
76758	Manzoor Ahmed	St # 6, Madni Mohallah	55
119492	Imran	St # 6,H # 10, Al Faisal Town	48
92610	Tehzeeb	St # 6,H # 21,A Block Al Faisal Town	48
99978	Jamil	St # 6,H # 314,Waseem Quarter	56
77874	Sagheer	St # 6/A,H # 471, Mehar Fiaz Colony A Block	55
6225	Rasheed	St # 62,Dar Ul Islam	54
83210	Khalid Abbas	St # 7,H # 6,Deen Muhammad Colony	55
26855	Liaqat Ali	St # 7,H # 6,Deen Muhammad Colony	55
21318	Qadeer	St # 8,H # 35,Faisal Park	43
111209	Abdurehman	St #10,H # 10,Tajpura	56
80821	Kamran	St #14,H# 275/C,Nazmabad	54
135345	Saleem Shehzad	St #57,H # 25,Mojahidabad	48
109735	M.Sadique	St #58,H # 366,Mojahidabad	48
85242	Mohsin	St# 6,H # 17,Takiya Mondran	60
122082	Sarwar	St#3 h#2 hira colony	56
11561	Faisal	St#8 H#11 lthad Town	56
103841	Rashid	St # 2,New Canal Park	55
102925	M.Ramzan	St # 21,H # 29,Androon Choubacha	55
69032	Asghar	St # 46,H # 11,Barkat Park	58
69389	Sagheer	St # 46,H # 42,Ittihad Colony Ghaziabad	55
3635	Baba Boota	St #3,H # 39,Shah Din Park	41
26297	Abdusattar	St # 18,Saraye Roshan Deen	55
59632	Haroon	St # 60,H # 4,Judge Block	55
134229	Salman	St # 8,H # 133	54
48401	Nadeem Akhtar	St # 9,H # 25,Shah Deen Park	55
131281	Tasleem	St #12,H # 4,Maskeen Pura	43
57243	Asif	St # 6,H # 369,Shalimar Housing Scheme	45

104756	Anwar	St # 53,H # 18	41
136818	Farhat	`St # 11,H # 24 C Block,Al Faisal Town	59
105314	Riaz	`St # 11,H # 31 C Block,Al Faisal Town	59
98504	M.Ishfaq	291 D Block Tajpura	55
82295	Kareem	317 B Block Tajpura	55
130924	Sabir Iqbal	6 B Block Tajpura	55
122998	Yaqoob	Ahata Laal Hussain Dry Port	45
45454	Anwar	Ahata Makhan Singh Dry Port	45
2161	Hameed Khan	Ali Muhammad Bazaar	57
30718	Tahir	Ali Muhammad Bazar	56
46370	Allah Ditta	Altaf Colony Hussain Road	56
36054	Shahid	Amer Tarsi Mohallah,St # 1,H # 35	56
67000	Mushtaq	Amir Town	55
112124	Salamat	B Block Tajpura	54
114714	Fareed	Badar Colony,St #1	48
33665	Jamshed	Badar Colony,St #1	54
37528	Khalid	Daira Ramzan Gujjar	60
62579	Ibrar	Dairy Painch	60
125387	Shehzad	Dargah Street Ahata Jamia Masjid Islam	59
74926	Amir	H #15,Near Umair School Altaf Colony	57
15066	Munir Masih	H #18,Jalal Colony	57
56685	Latif	H # 1,Block 57 Railway Quarter	56
5108	M.Altaf Hussain	H # 13D,Sali Town	59
21876	Salah-U-Din	H # 14,Main Bazaar Karako Mohallah	58
72895	Shafique	H # 14,Shamshan Bhoomi Mustafabad	57
94441	Nasir	H # 15,Ishwar Nagar	56
66442	Bashir	H # 16b,Fayaz Park	45
12476	Nadeem	H # 16fp,Fayaz Park	45
137734	Asif	H # 2,St # 24,Bus Sotp Ghaziabad	58
1246	Amjad	H # 20,Haji Pura	58
134787	M.Saqib	H # 207,Ghosia Colony	57
10087	Ghafoor Hussain	H # 22,Abubakar Block Pan Shop Gali Gujjar	56
108262	Ishaq	H # 239,Ahata Kshal Singh	45
89663	Qaiser	H # 287 St # 4 A Block Mehar Fiaz Colony	60
108820	Zeeshan	H # 305,Mian Line Railway Tariq Colony	54
51349	M.Sagheer	H # 312,Lda Suk Neher	48
122440	Shoukat Ali	H # 332 D Block Tajpura Scheme	60
83768	Zahoor	H # 332 D Block Tajpura Scheme	41
126503	Abbas	H # 36,Main Hussain Road Altaf Colony	58
136260	Zahid Saeed	H # 369,Shalimar Housing Scheme	57
5666	Niaz	H # 4,St # 12,Judge Block	45
121524	Nadeem	H # 43,LDA Muhammad Pura	44
49875	Ali Usman	H # 43A,LDA A ,Muhammad Pura	43
126861	M.Boota	H # 46,Main Canal Colony	60
70506	Ghullam Muhammad	H # 460,E Block Tajpura	60
28329	M.Bashir	H # 460,E Block Tajpura	60
16897	Abdul Aziz	H # 580 D Block Tajpura Scheme	41
124471	Bilal	H # 6,Quarters Dry Port	59
41033	Hameed Khan	H # 8 Larix Colony	57
15424	Tahir	H # 8,Main Infentary Road	56

128892	Allah Ditta	H # 8,Main Railway Line	56
27771	Mushtaq	H # 80,Khurram Block	55
55211	Shahid	H # 80,Khurram Block	56
9529	Salamat	H # 89,Nusrat Colony	54
8614	Jamshed	H # 898,St # 22,Mustafabad	54
112682	Fareed	H # 9,Main Infentary Road	48
76400	Khalid	H #22,Al Madina Street	60
10645	Ibrar	H #253,E Block Tajpura	60
69948	Shehzad	H #43,Mahtab Gali Taj Bagh	59
103283	Amir	H #9,Amir Town	57
3277	Munir Masih	H# 3 St# 4 Victory School	57
92052	Latif	H#102 St#21 Andron Chubacha	56
330	M.Altaf Hussain	H#24 Main Road Altaf Colony	59
100894	Salah-U-Din	H#29 st#23 gunj mughalpura	58
111767	Shafique	H#3 st#2 Haji Takiya	57
42507	Nasir	H#4 St#2 Allah Ho Bilding	56
11003	Nadeem	Hamid St # 1,Muslimabad	45
4193	Bashir	Hamid St # 1,Muslimabad	45
125945	Asif	Ismail Town Tall Wali Gali H # 37	58
36612	Amjad	Ismail Town Tall Wali Gali H # 5	58
28686	M.Saqib	Kachi Abadi Muhammad Pura H# 52	57
89105	Ghafoor Hussain	Madina Town	56
9172	Ishaq	Main Dispensary Road	45
74368	Qaiser	Main Railway Line St # 39	60
90020	Zeeshan	Main Tariq Colony Kachi Abadi	54
79705	M.Sagheer	Maqbool Park Saraye 36	48
110651	Zahoor	Millat Colony Kachi Abadi	41
119135	M.Boota	Millat Colony St#24	60
20403	M.Bashir	Millat Colony St#24 H#6	60
77316	Ghullam Muhammad	M-T Quarters	60
81178	Abdul Aziz	Quarter	41
106230	Shoukat Ali	Quarter No.3-4	60
132398	Abbas	Quarter Steel Mill Ghazi Peer	58
118577	Zahid Saeed	railway line muslim abad	57
58717	Niaz	Scheme No.1 Dharpura	45
100335	Nadeem	Shahid Town Choudhary Colony	44
12119	Ali Usman	Shehnaz Clinic Wali Gali Qalandarpura	43
65527	Khadim	St # 2,Hanif Park	59
116545	Tallat Saddiqe	St # 2,Hanif Park	59
101452	Ibrar Shah	St # 37,H # 17	55
73453	Khalil Ahmed	St # 4,H # 21,Razzaq Colony	55
19487	Khalid Mehmood	St # 5,H # 8,Nishter Town Darogawala	45
43422	Aslam	St # 6,H # 3,Razzaq Colony	45
44896	Amir	St # 6,H # 33,Razzaq Colony	43
40475	Farhat	St #1,H # 1,Bilal Park	59
53738	Riaz	St #1,H # 97,Nusrat Colony	59
13950	M.Ishfaq	St #2,H #2,Scheme 1	55
133313	Kareem	St #2,H # 10,Zohra Colony	55
14508	Sabir Iqbal	St #2,H # 41,Amin Park	55
94999	Yaqoob	St #42,H # 1	45

129450	Anwar	St #47,H # 2,Bhangali Mohallah	45
127419	Riaz	St #58,H # 55	58
32192	Adil	St #8/B,H # 24,Shah Deen Park	55
41949	Ahsan	St # 1,H # 1,Choungi Bazar	43
49317	Abdurazzaq	St # 1,H # 1,Riaz Pura	41
27213	Manzoor Hussian	St # 1,H # 10,Hameed Pura	59
93525	M. Arshad	St # 1,H # 10,Usman Nagar	59
133871	Ismail	St # 1,H # 11,Dar Ul Islam	48
114156	Shahid Mahmood	St # 1,H # 206/C,Guldasht C Block	57
48846	Arif	St # 1,H # 22,Salamat Pura Dairy	57
50320	Akhter Hussain	St # 1,H # 39,Bhangali Mohallah	43
45899	Gh.Rasool	St # 1,H # 4,Shah Deen Park	41
59162	Iqbal	St # 1,H # 5,Al Faisal Town	41
19374	Maqsood ul hasan	St # 1,H # 57,Badar Colony	59
37415	m.zubair	St # 1,H # 6,Akbar Park	59
56572	Naeem butt	St # 1,H # 6,Amer Tarsi Mohallah	59
100423	Nasir	St # 1,H # 6,Qlandar Pura	55
33552	Jamshad	St # 1,H # 7,Khalid Pco	54
31520	Salamat	St # 1,H # 7,Punj Peer	54
74255	Waheed	St # 1,Iftikhar Park Mohallah School Wala	43
47373	Rafique	St # 1,Medina Town	41
54741	Shafique	St # 1/A,H # 35,Habib Park	58
32637	Abdurazzaq	St # 10,H # 1,Masjid Quarters	57
98949	M.Azeem	St # 10,H # 14,Khan Colony	57
37973	Zahid Hussain	St # 10,H # 15,Hameed Pura	57
119580	Ghullam Murtaza	St # 10,H # 24,Ittihad Town	48
114043	S.Waqar Ali	St # 10,H# 9,Ghosia Colony	57
65972	Akhter	St # 10,Usman Nagar	41
35584	M.Sabir	St # 11,H # 10,Al-Madina Colony	60
90108	Abbas	St # 11,H # 103	58
64498	Liaqat	St # 11,H # 12,Punj Peer	58
40005	Ahsan	St # 11,H # 12,Punj Peer	58
76845	M.Akber	St # 11,H # 15,Al-Madina Colony	57
104286	Nazeer Ahmed	St # 11,H # 17,Badar Colony	57
58604	M.Nazeer	St # 11,H # 20,Gulshan Park	57
57688	M.Ali	St # 11,H # 20,Punj Peer	55
23795	Shakoor	St # 11,H # 36,Hameedp Pura	54
24152	Abid Hussain	St # 11A,H # 16,Faisal Park	43
96360	Naseer Ahmed	St # 12,H # 15,Qalandarpura	57
119022	Rashid	St # 12,H # 15,Qalandarpura	58
14395	M.Ilyas	St # 12,H # 17,Mohallah Fareedya	56
88991	Ayoob	St # 12,H # 19,Altaf Colony	55
3164	Shakeel	St # 12,H # 29,Peer Naseer	48
86044	Nisar Ahmed	St # 12,H # 31,Altaf Colony	48
12006	Afzal	St # 12,H # 8,Altaf Colony	44
59519	Ghullam Rasool	St # 13 ,H # 2,Kotli	43
91581	Muhammad sharif	St # 13,H # 1,Amir Town	60
60077	Shahzad	St # 13,H # 27,Altaf Colony	59
53267	Barkat	St # 14,H # 4,D Block Al Faisal Town	43
37057	Nayamat	St # 14,H #14,Al-Madina Colony	58

85687	Mazhar	St # 14,H #29,Al-Madina Colony	58
77761	Abbas	St # 14/A,H # 20/A/1,Hameed Pura	58
217	Saleem	St # 14B,H # 63,Hameed Pura	57
94886	Fahad	St # 15,H # 1,Gunj Bazaar	56
123443	Shahid	St # 15,H # 15 D Block Al Faisal Town	54
1132	Boota	St # 15,H # 23,Ali Muhammad Bazaar	43
128779	Sohail	St # 15,H # 40,Gunj Mughalpura	43
21763	Munir	St # 15,H # 41,	43
66887	Jawaid	St # 15,H # 8,Faisal Park	57
69477	Saleem	St # 15,H # 9	57
126390	Ishfaq	St # 16,H # 1, Altaf Colony	55
130253	Iqbal	St # 16,H # 35,Touheed Park	43
17342	Asif	St # 16,H # 8,Altaf Colony	43
80150	M.Islam	St # 16,Shah Deen Park Bilal Masjid	60
29689	M.Iqbal	St # 17,H # 12,Takya Mondranwala	57
107791	Nasir	St # 17,H # 33,Takya Mondra	55
11448	M.Yasir	St # 18	55
97833	M.Hanif	St # 18 ,H # 2,Kotli	55
114601	Jameel	St # 18,Darbar Wali Gali	54
27658	Nasir	St # 18,H # 24,Kotli Peer Abdurehman	45
49204	Nouman	St # 18,H # 4,Kotli Peer Abdurehman	43
21205	Sohail	St # 18,H # 7,Kotli Peer Abdurehman	58
105201	Hanif	St # 18,H # 7,Kotli Peer Abdurehman	58
92497	Nawaz	St # 19,H # 19,Kotli Peer Abdurehman	48
93970	Ali Akbar	St # 19,H # 2,Gunj Bazar	45
89550	M.Shafique	St # 19,H # 2,Gunj Bazar	45
102812	Zohaib	St # 19,H # 24,Kotli Peer Abdurehman	43
63024	Adeel	St # 19,Kothi Sarool Singh	43
44425	Iman	St # 2 H # 215 Larex Colony	44
63582	Yaseen	St # 2, Choungi Gujjar Pura	43
6111	Mehmood	St # 2, H # 10,Choungi Gujjar Pura	43
77203	Saif U Rehman	St # 2,H # 14,Al-Madina Colony	43
38531	Ata Muhammad	St # 2,H # 14,Al-Madina Colony	48
81266	Younas	St # 2,H # 146,Amir U Din	43
91023	Mustafa	St # 2,H # 151,Amir U Din Park	43
98391	Zulfiqar	St # 2,H # 151,Amir U Din Park	43
76287	Ishfaq	St # 2,H # 16,	43
4638	Rizwan	St # 2,H # 2,Amin Park	43
81623	Rizwan	St # 2,H # 2,Muslim Abad	60
25268	Zubair	St # 2,H # 20,Ghazi Peer	59
121054	M.Javid	St # 2,H # 26,Iftikhar Park Mohallah Bagh	59
109622	Zulfiqar	St # 2,H # 331	55
79234	Tariq	St # 2,H # 4,Choudhary Colony	54
133758	Hashmat	St # 2,H # 4,Shah Deen Park	45
108148	Lateef	St # 2,H # 55,Androon Choubacha	44
83655	Ashraf	St # 2,H # 57,Noor Colony	41
120495	Razzaq	St # 2,H # 58,Gulshan Park	41
9974	Niaz Khan	St # 2,H # 6,Hameed Pura	45
102254	Iftikhar	St # 2,H # 6,Muslim Abad	45
101338	Lal Din	St # 2,H # 7,Qalandarpura	43

67445	Ismail	St # 2,H # 8,Gujja Peer Road	60
31163	Shoukat	St # 2,H # 8,Qalandar Pura	60
103370	Ajmal	St # 2,H # 8,Riaz Pura	60
24710	Mushtaq	St # 2,H # 97,Androon Choubacha	60
58045	Ishaq	St # 2,H #24,Al-Madina Colony	60
96002	Ahmad Khan	St # 2, Madina Town	59
46815	Naseem	St # 2,Qalandarura Gulistan Colony	58
93055	M.Noor	St # 20,H # 1,Rashidpura	60
55656	Anees	St # 20,H # 13,D Block Al Faisal Town	57
66530	Ramzan	St # 20,H # 16,Javaid Colony	57
135232	Tayaba	St # 20,H # 16,Rasheed Pura	55
103728	Khursheed	St # 20,H # 16,Touheed Park	54
96918	Riaz	St # 20,H # 21,Touheed Park	44
80708	M.Munir	St # 20,H # 24	60
129337	Fiaz	St # 20,H # 6,Rasheedpura	55
121411	Ameer Hamza	St # 20,H #6,Amir Town	54
43867	Hanif	St # 20,h# 36 d block al faisal town	54
101897	Shafique	St # 21,H # 104,Androon Choubacha	44
29131	Rasheed Khan	St # 21,H # 104,Androon Choubacha	48
44783	Shafaqat Ali	St # 21,H # 14	44
34468	Maqsood	St # 21,H # 14,D Block Al Faisal Town	60
65414	Ayaz	St # 21,H # 18,D Block Al Faisal Town	60
73898	Mehmood	St # 22,H # 232,Bhatta Chabeel	45
113127	Munawar Ajmal	St # 22,H # 50,Bhatta Chabeel	60
32078	Waris	St # 22,H # 572,Shalimar Scheme	60
35941	Shahid	St # 22,H# 27,Bhatta Chabeel	59
60993	Ishtiaq	St # 23	57
87160	Abdul Hameed	St # 23,H # 36,gunj mughalpura	56
73340	M.Saleem	St # 24,H # 13,Dogar Road	55
13479	Pappu	St # 24,H # 15,Dogar Road	55
55098	Jameel	St # 24,H # 6,Hunabad	45
104844	Qurban Ali Shah	St # 25 H # 1 Wali Park	45
20289	Hussain	St # 25,H # 1,Wali Park	60
71308	Allah Rakha	St # 25,H # 19,Wali Park	60
56214	M.Arshad	St # 25,H # 30,Nima Wala Bazaar	60
28216	Munir	St # 25,Mehar Fiaz Colony A Block	59
112212	Ramzan	St # 26 H # 2 Wali Park	59
136147	Ali Akbar	St # 26,H # 25,Wali Park	56
137621	Abdul Aziz	St # 26,H # 4,Wali Park	56
133200	Aslam	St # 26,H # 515,Gulistan Colony	56
8501	Nawaz	St # 27,H # 110,Mian Tariq Line	48
106675	Sharif	St # 27,H # 608	45
88076	Sajjad	St # 27,H # 800,Mustafabad	44
107233	Ramzan	St # 28,H # 2	41
49762	Sanobil	St # 28,H # 39,Muradpura	60
84213	Ashraf	St # 28,H # 4,Muradpura	60
82181	M.Ijaz	St # 28,H# 3,Gunj Bazar	60
124916	Arif	St # 29,H # 5,Murad Pura Fateh Garh	60
134674	Fazal	St # 29,H # 6,Quraishi Mohallah	59
4080	Qamar	St # 2a,H # 2,Akbar Park	59

119937	Azhar	St # 3 ,B Block Qalandar Pura	58
48288	Rafique	St # 3,H #10,Taj Mahal Park Bhatta Gadiya	56
88634	Shafique	St # 3,H # 1, Mashraqi Mohallah	56
68919	Qamar Zaman	St # 3,H # 1,Bismillah Park	56
26742	Nasir	St # 3,H # 1,Takya Mondran	55
116633	Hanif Lodhi	St # 3,H # 10,Rasool Pura	55
122885	Tariq Mahmood	St # 3,H # 11,Riaz Pura	55
39447	Khalid	St # 3,H # 15,Ghazi Peer Darbar	48
115159	Asia Bibi	St # 3,H # 2/A,Gunj Bazar	60
127306	M.Sadique	St # 3,H # 20,Imam Town Gujja Peer	60
26184	Mehboob Hussain	St # 3,H # 21,Al Faisal Town	60
53625	Akber Ali	St # 3,H # 23	60
109265	Mehmood	St # 3,H # 24,Mian Park	59
7027	Rafique	St # 3,H # 27,Usman Nagar	59
111096	Khursheed	St # 3,H # 3,Gujja Peer Road	58
74813	Nasir	St # 3,H # 3,Janazgah	58
9059	M.Arshad	St # 3,H # 32,Ali Muhammad Bazaar	57
68361	Sadique	St # 3,H # 323,Muslim Abad	48
65056	Kashif	St # 3,H # 5,Qalandarpura	41
1691	Amin	St # 3,H # 5,Razzaq Colony	41
90465	Safdar	St # 3,H # 56, Mustafabad	41
136705	Abdul Ghafoor	St # 3,H # 6 A Block Al Faisal Town	60
99307	Muhammad Lateef	St # 3,H # 6,Gunj Bazar	60
110180	Muhammad Shafique	St # 3,H # 6,Noor Colony	60
40920	Abdul Rehman	St # 3,H # 7,Bismillah Park	59
110738	Muhammad Ali	St # 3,H # 7,Ghosia Colony	59
2606	Muhammad Siddique	St # 3,H # 9,Fiaz Park	57
124358	Javaid	St # 3,H # 9,Fiaz Park	57
35026	Fahad	St # 3,H # 9,Noor Colony	56
27100	Zamin	St # 3,Muslim Abad Noori Darbar Road	44
87518	M.Imran	St # 30,H # 10,Fateh Garh	60
7585	Sadiq	St # 30,H # 102 Fateh Garh	60
72782	Rizwan	St # 30,H # 14,A Block Al Faisal Town	60
51794	Tufail	St # 30,H # 4,Rasheedpura	60
41478	Shabbier	St # 31,H # 11,Chand Jeweler Wali Gali	60
72424	M.Hussain	St # 31,H # 2,Chand Jeweler Wali Gali	60
117548	Sohail	St # 31,H # 2,Nima Wala Bazaar No.1	60
18816	M.Saleem	St # 31,H # 7,Muslimabad	59
75729	Shoukat	St # 31,Rasheedpura	56
42952	Ishtiaq	St # 31,Rasheedpura	57
68003	Rizwan	St # 32,H # 10,Hussain Pura	48
130811	Azeem	St # 32,H # 12,Main Bazaar Dharampura	44
116990	Aslam	St # 32,H # 15,Gunj Bazaar	44
57130	Ashraf	St # 32,H # 22,Hussain Pura	44
62109	Akbar	St # 32,H # 8,Hussain Pura	44
10532	Ali Hamza	St # 32,H #26,Mustafabad	60
63940	Pervaiz	St # 32,H #26,Mustafabad	60
78319	Lateef	St # 32,Hussain Pura	58
99865	Shafique	St # 32,Hussain Pura	58
71866	Ashraf	St # 32,Hussain Pura	58

17900	Faryad	St # 33,H # 135,Malak Park	56
41836	M.Boota	St # 33,H # 135,Malak Park	57
43309	Ahsan	St # 33,H # 4,Usman Block Choungi Gujjar Pura	56
38888	Imran	St # 34,H # 8/A,Gunj Bazaar	44
52151	M.Akbar	St # 35,H # 2	60
113685	Ishtaiq	St # 35,H # 204	60
131726	Muhayudin	St # 35,H # 6	58
12921	Sajjad	St # 36,H # 3,Gunj Bazaar	58
93412	Ahsan	St # 36,H # 44,Gunj Mughalpura	58
127864	Shafique	St # 36,H # 7,Muslim Abad	58
125832	Ishfaq	St # 38,H # 1/2,Madina Mohallah	45
30605	Ali Usman	St # 38,H # 13	43
40362	Latif	St # 38,H # 13,Gunj Mughalpura	60
47730	Shehzad	St # 38,H # 13,Gunj Mughalpura	60
25626	Noor Ilahi	St # 38,H # 14,Mustafabad	59
91939	Arshad	St # 38,H # 7,Bhangali Mohallah	58
132284	Asif Iqbal	St # 38,H # 7,Bhangali Mohallah	59
112569	Osaf	St # 39,H # 176,Mojahidabad	58
70392	Nisar	St # 39,H # 205	58
22321	Safyan	St # 39,H# 429,Mojahidabad	57
28573	Akhter	St # 39,H# 430,Mojahidabad	56
83097	Khalid	St # 39,Muslim Abad	45
20848	Raees Butt	St # 39,Muslim Abad	48
32994	Amir	St # 39,Muslim Abad	48
69834	Ramzan	St # 3a,H # 3,Razzaq Colony	44
60635	Iqbal	St # 4 H # 9 Allah hu Building	60
14953	Munir	St # 4,Fateh Garh Allah Hoo Building	59
50677	Rafaqat	St # 4,H # 24,Al Faisal Town	58
118106	Munir Ahmed	St # 4,H # 1,Al Hajvairy	56
118464	M.Qadeer	St # 4,H # 11/C,Karmanwala	48
52709	Abdulslam	St # 4,H # 19,Bhatta Gadiyan	48
75371	Ameer Ahmed	St # 4,H # 2,Bilal Park	48
108707	Taj Deen	St # 4,H # 2,Hameed Pura	45
45341	Rehman	St # 4,H # 25,Muhammad Pura	43
97476	Ilyas	St # 4,H # 28,Qalandar Pura	60
42394	Bashir	St # 4,H # 3,Ghosia Colony	59
106317	Manzoor	St # 4,H # 30,E Block	59
15869	Nazeer Ahmed	St # 4,H # 33,Muhammad Pura	57
84571	Sarfraz	St # 4,H # 4,Touheed Park	57
16427	M.Saleem	St # 4,H # 46,New Canal Park	56
46257	Abdurehman	St # 4,H # 46,New Canal Park	56
30047	Shabbir Hussain	St # 4,H # 57 Outside Office	55
78676	Abid Ali	St # 4,H # 6,Gujja Peer Road	55
34110	Abdulatif	St # 4,H # 9,Saraye Jorra Peer	48
94528	Afsheen	St # 4,H# 5,Ghosia Colony	44
51235	Munir Ahmed	St # 4,Madina Town	44
79792	Allah Rakha	St # 4,Manzoor Colony Taj Bagh	41
95444	Bashir	St # 4,Manzoor Colony Taj Bagh	41
85129	Younas	St # 4,Manzoor Colony Taj Bagh	43
116075	Niamat	St # 4,Shah Deen Park	58

23237	Shahid	St # 4,Taj Bagh	58
62466	Hamoyon Tariq	St # 4/5,H # 4,Gujja Peer Road	56
82740	Mian	St # 40,H # 10,Military Accounts Colony	55
86602	Imtiaz	St # 42, Maqbool Park	54
111654	Shafique	St # 42,H # 105,Quarter	48
36499	Nawaz Khan	St # 42,H # 3,Maqbool Park	44
22679	Abdul Wahid	St # 42,H # 3/A,Habibya Colony	43
100780	Zulfiqar	St # 42,H # 3/A,Habibya Colony	43
105759	Abdurazzaq	St # 42,H # 4	41
54183	Asghar	St # 42,H # 4	43
70951	Ashraf	St # 42,H # 4/B,Gulistan Colony	41
121969	Nasir	St # 42,H # 47,Habibya Colony	41
5553	Imran	St # 42,H # 47,Habibya Colony	41
115517	Shehzad	St # 42,H # 9	60
61551	M.Ilyas	St # 43,H # 10,Quarter No.1,Ishfaq Pura	60
16627	Basharat	St # 44,H # 2,Mustafabad	59
418	M.Zubair	St # 44,H # 2,Mustafabad	59
49047	Shafique	St # 44,H # 24,Suk Neher	57
41121	M.Rafique	St # 44,H # 34,Suk Neher	56
101539	Munawar Hussain	St # 44,H # 44,Suk Neher	56
58246	Shehzad	St # 44,H # 5,Madina Mohallah	54
86803	Imtiaz	St # 44,H # 9	54
102455	Amin	St # 45,H # 11,Military Accounts Colony	54
92139	Imran	St # 45/B,Muslim Mohallah	45
123085	Abid	St # 45/C, Bhangali Mohallah	45
30247	Raza	St # 45/C,H # 1,Bhangali Mohallah	43
32837	M.Nadeem	St # 45b,Bhangali Mohallah	60
89750	M.Khalid	St # 45B,H # 31,Madina Mohallah	60
93613	Ghullam Abbas	St # 45B,H # 42,Madina Mohallah	59
118664	Ramzan	St # 45B,H # 6,Madina Mohallah	59
43510	Abid	St # 45B,Madina Mohallah	58
131011	Asghar Ali	St # 45b,Madina Mohallah	59
71151	Iftikhar	St # 45c,Bhangali Mohallah	58
112770	Amjad	St # 45c,H # 117,Ittihad Colony	58
61193	Arshad	St # 45c,H # 19,Bhangali Mohallah	58
77961	Adrees	St # 45c,H # 31,Bhangali Mohallah	58
128980	M.Yaseen	St # 46,H # 12,Barkat Park	57
12564	Saleem	St # 46,H # 20,Barkat Park	56
122527	Faryad Hussain	St # 46,H # 24,Hafiz Park	56
68561	Ali Nawaz	St # 46,H # 33,Barkat Park	56
55857	Ashraf	St # 46,H # 42,Ittihad Colony Ghaziabad	54
57331	Zafar Ali Shahid	St # 46,H # 58/100,Bismillah Street	54
52910	Awal Khan	St # 46,H # 6,Ittihad Colony Ghaziabad	45
66172	Altaf	St # 46,H # 7,Ittihad Colony Ghaziabad	45
26385	Shahid	St # 46,H # 7,Ittihad Colony Ghaziabad	45
7786	Sohail	St # 46,H # 95,Barkat Park Main Road	45
26943	Basher	St # 46,H # 95,Barkat Park Main Road	45
107434	Iqbal	St # 46/C,H # 184,Barkat Park	45
40563	Amjad Ali	St # 46/C,H # 37,Barkat Park	60
1891	Ishfaq	St # 46/C,H # 37,Barkat Park	44

44626	Khizar	St # 48,H # 12A ,Mustafabad	58
54383	Rana Shimar	St # 49,H # 19,Ishfaq Pura	57
61751	Barkat Ali	St # 49,H # 19,Ishfaq Pura	57
39647	M.Iqbal	St # 49,H # 408,Mojahidabad	57
105960	Haroon	St # 49,H # 49,Ittihad Colony	56
44984	Sabir	St # 49,H # 49,Ittihad Colony	56
126591	Qasim	St # 49,H # 63,Ittihad Colony	55
84414	Shafaqat Ali	St # 4a,H # 33,Mojahidabad	54
72982	Shahbaz	St # 4d,H # 4,Bhangali Mohallah	54
42594	Jahngeer	St # 5 H # 51 Allah hu Building	48
97118	Nasir Ishaq	St # 5,H # 1,Shah Deen Park Tall Wali Gali	48
71509	M.Rafique	St # 5,H # 11,Dar-UI-Islam	48
47015	M.Arif	St # 5,H # 11,Habib Block Dogaich	48
83856	Riaz	St # 5,H # 11,Husnabad	48
111296	Rafique	St # 5,H # 117,Shaheen Park	44
65614	Ayoob	St # 5,H # 12,Karmanwala	44
64699	Mushtaq	St # 5,H # 13,Altaf Colony	44
30805	Deen Muhammd	St # 5,H # 13,Altaf Colony	44
132485	Shafique	St # 5,H # 13,Altaf Colony	44
66730	Akbar Ali	St # 5,H # 13,Karmanwala	44
126033	Ubaid	St # 5,H # 14,Husnabad	43
21406	Shahid	St # 5,H # 14,Karmanwala	43
59362	Anwar	St # 5,H # 15 A Block Al Faisal Town	41
10175	Ashiq	St # 5,H # 15 A Block Al Faisal Town	41
56415	Allah Dittah	St # 5,H # 16,Karmanwala	59
19016	M.Riaz	St # 5,H # 17,Karmanwala	59
29890	Raza	St # 5,H # 18,Karmanwala	58
98592	Shahbaz	St # 5,H # 2 D Block Al Faisal Town	58
67088	M.Sabir	St # 5,H # 2,Husnabad	55
60278	Tariq Mubeen	St # 5,H # 28,Nazir Garden	54
44068	Imran	St # 5,H # 3,Habib Block Dogaich	54
92697	Hamid Mahmood	St # 5,H # 36,Shaheen Park	48
84771	Umair	St # 5,H # 38,Choudhary Colony	48
7228	Nazar	St # 5,H # 4,Nazmabad	60
65257	Nadeem	St # 5,H # 47,Altaf Colony	60
130453	Faheem Shehzad	St # 5,H # 49,Altaf Colony	60
8143	Shehzad	St # 5,H # 49,Dispencery Road	60
135790	Ashiq	St # 5,H # 5,Dispencery Road	58
28774	Imran	St # 5,H # 5,Faisal Park	58
37258	Ghullam Rasool	St # 5,H # 5,Gujja Peer Road	58
76488	Imran	St # 5,H # 5,Gunj Bazaar	58
133401	Arshad	St # 5,H # 51,Muradpura	55
137263	Shabbier	St # 5,H # 7,Husnabad	55
24353	Zeeshan	St # 5,H # 9,Husnabad	54
50521	Shahbaz	St # 5,H # 9,Karmanwala	48
36700	Imran	St # 5,Husnabad	41
114802	Arshad Ali	St # 5,Larex Colony	41
18458	Abdul Razzaq	St # 5,Muslim Abad	41
68204	Ashraf	St # 5,Muslim Abad	41
121612	Hameed	St # 5/3,H # 18,Gujja Peer Road	60

34668	M.Sadique	St # 5/3,H # 2	60
19575	Shabbier	St # 50, Ishfaq Pura	60
129538	Riaz	St # 50,H # 159,Mojahid Abad	59
75572	Asif	St # 50a,H # 4a,Mojahidabad	58
99507	Hameed	St # 51,H # 13,Ittihad Colony	56
100981	Shafique	St # 51,H # 15	56
96560	Zulfiqar	St # 51,H # 2,Ittihad Colony	56
109823	Khalid	St # 52,H # 3,Mojahid Abad	54
70035	Ali	St # 52,H # 5,Mojahid Abad	54
51436	Rasheed Khan	St # 52,H# 5,Mojahidabad	48
70593	Abdul Hanan	St # 53,H # 11,Mojahidabad	48
13122	Sharafat	St # 53,H # 13,Mian Meer	43
47573	Aziz	St # 53,H # 18,Ghaziabad	41
45542	Kashif	St # 53,H # 18,Ghaziabad	41
88277	Shahid Iqbal	St # 53,H # 19	60
98034	Sharif	St # 53,H # 20/12	56
105402	Iqra	St # 53,H # 22/4,Mian Meer	56
83298	Inam Ali	St # 53,H # 37	55
11648	Shahid	St # 53,H # 42,Ittihad Colony	55
51994	Kashif Nadeem	St # 53,H # 5,Mian Meer	55
32279	M.Boota	St # 53,H # 5,Mian Meer	55
128064	Farooq	St # 53,H # 53,Ittihad Colony	54
79993	Tallat	St # 53,H # 7,Ittihad Colony	54
86245	Perwaiz	St # 53,Ittihad Colony	48
2807	Iftikhar	St # 54,H# 1	48
78519	Zamin	St # 55,H # 20,Mojahidabad	44
90666	Tariq	St # 55,H # 24/A,Mojahidabad	44
127506	Salamat	St # 55,H # 44,Mojahidabad	44
16985	Raouf	St # 55,H # 67,Mojahidabad	44
72625	Shafique	St # 55,H # 707 LDA ,Mojahidabad	41
108349	Abdul Gafoor	St # 55,H # 707,Mojahid Abad	41
74456	Kashif	St # 56,H # 101,Mojahidabad	41
38174	Shakeel	St # 56,H # 18/A,Ittihad Colony	41
110381	Javid	St # 56,Ittihad Colony Quaid-E-Azam School Wali Gali	41
31721	Ashiq	St # 57,H # 316,Mojahidabad	41
28416	Irshad	St # 58,H #3,Mustafabad	41
103013	Ramzan	St # 58,H # 19	41
53825	Sadiq	St # 58,H # 55,Mustafabad	41
100065	Jameel Amir Shah	St # 59,H # 15,Muslim Mohallah	60
62667	Gulzar Hussain	St # 5a,H # 2,	60
73540	Mubarak	St # 5a,H # 7,Gunj Bazar	58
4280	Mukhtar	St # 5A,H # 7B,Shah Kamal Road	58
74098	M.Akram	St # 5B,H # 13,Gunj Bazar	56
103928	Munir	St # 5B,H # 13,Gunj Bazar	56
87718	Saleem Shehzad	St # 6,H # 10 A Block	48
136348	Munawar Baig	St # 6,H # 13,Usman Block Choungi Gujjar Pura	45
128422	Rehman	St # 6,H # 14,Taj Bagh Sami Town	44
50878	Fayyaz	St # 6,H # 20,Sami Town	54
108907	Abdul Ghafoor	St # 6,H # 25,Wali Park	48
36142	Ata Ullah	St # 6,H # 26,Al-Madina Colony	48

15154	Babar	St # 6,H # 27, Usman Block Choungi Gujjar Pura	44
4838	Javaid	St # 6,H # 3	44
35784	Sultan	St # 6,H # 36,Faisal Park	45
80908	Mushtaq	St # 6,H # 36,Faisal Park	45
120138	Mehmood	St # 6,H # 5,Shah Deen Park	43
39089	M. Aslam	St # 6,H # 6 ,Shah Deen Park	43
6312	Naeem	St # 6,H # 6 A Block Al Faisal Town	43
31363	Arshad	St # 6,H # 6,Ishwar Nagar	60
94171	M.Azeem	St # 6,H # 64,A Block Al Faisal Town	60
80350	Babar Hussain	St # 6,H # 7 A Block	60
20490	Nadeem	St # 6,H # 7,Mian Meer	60
25469	Mushtaq	St # 6,H #1, Riaz Pura	58
111854	Saeed Ahmed	St # 6,H# 12A	57
27300	Manzoor	St # 6,H# 13,Dar-UI-Islam	56
41679	Allah Ditta	St # 6,H# 14,Dar-UI-Islam	56
63225	Sarwar	St # 60,H # 189,Judge Block	55
35226	Nadeem	St # 62,H # 2,Dar-UI-Islam	48
119222	Adrees	St # 62,H # 33	48
5196	M.Yousaf	St # 62,H # 51,Main Ganda Nala	48
6669	Naseer	St # 62,H #1,Ganda Nala	48
2249	Aslam	St # 62,Main Ganda Nala	48
15511	Latif	St # 63, ganda nala	45
77046	Akram	St # 63,H # 18,Ganda Nala	45
95087	Faiz Ahmed	St # 63,H # 21,Dar UI Islam	45
114244	Rafi	St # 64,H # 10	44
56772	Qaiser	St # 64,H # 239,Ayaz Town	44
91224	Gulzar	St # 64,H # 30,Tanvirabad	60
89192	Waseem	St # 64,H # 37,Tanvirabad	59
131927	Buhadar Khan	St # 64,H # 48,Tanvirabad	57
3722	M.Khatib	St # 64,H # 48,Tanvirabad	57
11090	M.Raees	St # 64,H # 5,Tanvirabad	56
126948	Zakir Hussain	St # 64,H # 5,Tanvirabad	56
55299	Chanda Bhi	St # 65,H # 2,Mutafabad	56
95645	Muhammad Hussain	St # 65,H # 295 Main Railway Line	55
75929	Manzoor Shah	St # 65,H # 313,Mustafabad	54
33753	Mushtaq	St # 6A	48
123643	M.Afzaal	St # 6a,Rasheeda Hospital Wali Gali	48
129895	Khalid Mahmood	St # 6-B,H #18,Mustafabad	48
46457	Mahmood Akhtar	St # 7,H # 10,Choudhary Colony	45
122170	Sajid	St # 7,H # 10,Choudhary Colony	45
134316	Saeed	St # 7,H # 10,Faisal Park	45
33195	Amjad	St # 7,H # 14,A Block Al Faisal Town	44
23995	Shahid	St # 7,H # 14,Tajpura	44
116275	Amjad	St # 7,H # 16,Deen Muhammad Colony	44
14038	Anees	St # 7,H # 17,Deen Muhammad Colony	43
81466	Abdurauoof	St # 7,H # 19,Tajpura	60
81824	Khalid Mahmood	St # 7,H # 2,Deen Muhammad Colony	60
16069	Khalid Khan	St # 7,H # 20,Muhammad Pura	60
38732	M.Rafique	St # 7,H # 22 C Block Al-Faisal Town	59
72067	M.Riaz	St # 7,H # 25,Razzaq Colony	59

8701	Rafi	St # 7,H # 27,Deen Muhammad Colony	58
60836	Anjum	St # 7,H # 28 C Block Al-Faisal Town	57
5754	Yaseen	St # 7,H # 30 A Block Al Faisal Town	57
69678	Naeem	St # 7,H # 32,Deen Muhammad Colony	57
117191	Manzoor Hussain	St # 7,H # 32,Faisal Park	57
47931	Ijaz	St # 7,H # 4,Bhutto Colony	56
117749	Sabar	St # 7,H # 5,Dar-UI-Islam	55
9617	M.Anwar	St # 7,H # 5,Deen Muhammad Colony	55
131369	Naeem	St # 7,H # 6,Deen Muhammad Colony	54
42036	Ghullam Hussain	St # 7,H # 6,Karmanwala	48
135432	Yahya	St # 7,H # 8,Deen Muhammad Colony	43
57889	Rashid	St # 7,H # 82,Deen Muhammad Colony	43
14596	Zaheer	St # 7,H# 19,A Block Al Faisal Town	43
43152	Asif	St # 7,Mehar Fiaz Colony	43
58804	Asif	St # 7,Rasool Pura	58
48489	Altaf	St # 71,H# 27,Ittihad Colony	57
79435	Hadayat Ali	St # 8 H # 6 Muhallah Murad Pura	56
124559	Nasir	St # 8,H # 1,Rasheedpura	55
25826	Rana Sohail	St # 8,H # 15,B Block Al Faisal Town	48
46100	Arif	St # 8,H # 162	45
49962	Rafique	St # 8,H # 18,Main Road Husnabad	45
75014	Ishfaq	St # 8,H # 24,Shah Deen Park	45
137821	Yaqoob	St # 8,H # 24,Shah Deen Park	45
124001	Musarrat	St # 8,H # 28,Faisal Park	44
64141	M.Ramzan	St # 8,H # 7,Faisal Park	41
69119	Ishfaq Ahmed	St # 8,H# 10	60
17543	M.Rasheed	St # 8,Main Boundary B Block	60
34311	Munawar	St # 8/B,H # 6,Dogaich Bazaar	60
85329	Riaz	St # 8/B,H # 7,Dogaich Bazaar	58
106875	M.Sadiq	St # 8b,H # 14,Shah Deen Park	57
78877	Mojahid Latif	St # 9,H # 1	57
24911	Mushtaq	St # 9,H # 103,Habibya Colony	56
12206	Shafique	St # 9,H # 21,B Block	56
13680	Allah Rakhi	St # 9,H # 22,Main Bazaar Dharampura	56
9259	Zohra	St # 9,H # 24,D Block Kal-Faisal Town	55
22522	Tariq Mahmood	St # 9,H #4,Nazmabad	55
120696	Salamat	St # 9,Hameed Pura	54
775	Moeen	St # 9,Mehar Fiaz Colony	54
19932	Tanvir	St # 98,Muslim Mohallah	54
63783	Shehzad	St # B/13,H # 24,Shah Deen Park	54
134874	Yar Muhammad	St #1 Dar Ul Islam	54
132843	Farooq	St #1,H # 130/A,Shalimar Scheme	48
37615	Usman	St #1,H # 15 R-A Wali Gali Qalandarpura	48
10733	Allah Dittah	St #1,H # 16,Fiaz Park	45
18101	Anwar Bibi	St #1,H # 18,Dogiach Town	45
133959	Aleem	St #1,H # 20,Ahata Makhan Singh	45
62309	Aslam	St #1,H # 4 R-A Wali Gali Qalandarpura	60
1333	Mahmood	St #1,H # 4 R-A Wali Gali Qalandarpura	43
82940	M.Amin	St #1,H # 46,Zubair Block	59
77403	Talib Hassan	St #1,H # 50,Mehar Fiaz Colony	59

29332	Abdul Haq	St #1,H # 6,Shalimar Scheme A Block	57
136906	Kamran Abbas	St #1,H# 1,Nazmabad	57
53468	Abdul Majeed	St #1,H# 1,Nazmabad	57
27858	Ameer Khan	St #1,H# 2,Gujja Peer Road	57
3365	M.Qasim	St #1,H# 4,Nazmabad	57
40205	Basher Ahmed	St #1,Quarter No.1 Nimko Wala Ahata	57
67646	M.Rafique	St #1/A,Riaz Pura	56
21964	Shahid Hussain	St #1/A,Riaz Pura	57
21048	Tariq	St #10,H # 17,B Block Al Faisal Town	56
125117	Zahid	St #10,H # 18,Al Madina Colony	56
125474	Qasim	St #10,H # 33,Shahid Park	55
59720	Naveed	St #10,H # 34,Ismail Town	54
82382	Shahbaz	St #10,H # 8,Shahid Park	54
115717	Mansoor	St #10,H# 6,Tajpura	45
52352	Younas	St #11,H # 1/B,Usman Nagar	45
104486	Basher Ahmed	St #11,H # 9,Taj Bagh	45
49404	Sadique	St #12,H # 1,Gulshan Park	45
113328	Imran	St #12,H # 11,B Block Al Faisal Town	44
22879	Yousaf	St #12,H # 2,Gulshan Park	44
54941	Shehzad	St #12,H # 20,Zubair Block	44
23437	Irfan	St #12,H # 23,Zubair Block	44
90622	Abdulatif	St #12,H # 25,Gulshan Park	44
15467	Sadiq	St #12,H # 31,Zubair Block	44
102969	Mushtaq	St #12,H # 4,Maskeen Pura	43
43109	Abdurazzaq	St #12,H # 5,Mustafabad	59
84727	Tahir	St #12,H # 5,Mustafabad	60
33151	Taimoor	St #12,H #16,C Block Al Faisal Town	59
49919	Akhter	St #12,H #16,C Block Al Faisal Town	59
100937	Basher Ahmed	St #12,H #42,C Block Al Faisal Town	59
122483	Abdurasheed	St #13,H # 27,Al Faisal Town	57
94485	M.Yousaf	St #13,H# 6,D Block Al Faisal Town	57
40519	Gull Agha Khan	St #14,H # 18 D Block Al Faisal Town	57
27814	Amir Rasheed	St #14,H # 25 D Block Al Faisal Town	57
29288	Fazal U Rehman	St #14,H # 9 D Block Al Faisal Town	57
24867	Zulfiqar	St #14,H #16,C Block Al Faisal Town	56
38130	Ibrahim	St #14,H #16,C Block Al Faisal Town	57
136304	M.Arif	St #15,H # 29/1,Gunj Bazar	48
117705	Bashir Ahmed	St #15,H # 29/1,Gunj Bazar	48
136862	Asif	St #15,H # 496,Mustafabad	48
79391	Khalid	St #16,H # 14,Hussain Pura	44
12520	Boota	St #16,H # 31,Al-Madina Colony	44
111811	Afzal	St #16,H # 31,Al-Madina Colony	44
16584	Nazeer	St #16,H # 37,Al-Madina Colony	44
26341	Arshad	St #18,Band Gali No.1 Nimko Wala Ahata	44
33709	Serwar	St #18,H # 1,Kotli	44
11605	Asghar Ali	St #18,H # 18,Faisal Park	43
77917	Saleem	St #18,H # 19,Kotli	43
16941	Zulfiqar	St #18,H # 2,Al Faisal Town	41
98548	Tasawar	St #18,H # 2,Kotli	41
56371	Hafeez Ahmed	St #18,H # 9,Al Faisal Town	58

44940	M.Arshad	St #19,H # 1,Tajpura	56
14552	Nawaz	St #2,Dharampura Bazar	48
69076	Tanvir Ahmed	St #2,Dharampura Bazar	54
43466	Tariq	St #2,H # 1, C Block Al Faisal Town	44
18973	Ghullam Mustafa	St #2,H # 10,Fiaz Park	43
55813	Younas	St #2,H # 13,Al Faisal Town	43
83254	Shakeel	St #2,H # 13,Al Faisal Town	43
37572	Ishaq	St #2,H # 16,Al Faisal Town	43
36656	Rehmat	St #2,H # 16,Al Faisal Town	43
2763	Imran	St #2,H # 31,Hajvairy Block	54
104443	M.Latif	St #2,H # 5	60
38688	Naimat Khan	St #2,H # 6,Razzaq Colony	60
97990	Furqan	St #2,H #89,Choudhary Yaqoob Haviyal	41
131325	Azman	St #2,H #89,Choudhary Yaqoob Haviyal	41
31320	Kashif	St #2,Shah Deen Park	41
120094	Umar Ashraf	St #20,H # 13,Javaid Colony	41
28373	Ashiq Hussain	St #20,H # 25,Javaid Colony	41
128936	Rafique	St #23,H # 12,Mojahidabad	56
1847	Babo Kanan	St #26,H # 10	56
70549	Shahid	St #26,H # 41,Muslim Abad	56
39045	Abid	St #26,H # 44,Muslim Abad	44
32235	Patras Masih	St #26,H # 44,Muslim Abad	44
16025	Binyameen	St #27,H # 608,Mustafabad	44
64655	Younas	St #27,Hussain Pura	43
56729	Aziz	St #27,Tariq Colony	60
117147	Akram	St #27,Tariq Colony	41
37214	Hanif	St #27,Tariq Colony	43
102411	Aslam	St #27,Tariq Colony	43
118063	Mehmood	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	59
107747	Ashraf	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	57
731	Akmal	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	45
9215	M Arfan	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	56
48445	M. Faheem	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	56
105358	M Arif	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	56
109221	M Mushtaq	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	56
134272	Umrar Farooq	St #28,Mohallah Fareediya	54
22478	Khalid	St #3,H # 1,Hira Colony	48
8657	Umar	St #3,H # 22 A Block Al Faisal Town	44
86759	Taj Deen	St #3,h # 3,chaman park	44
128378	Shoukat	St #3,H # 39,Shah Din Park	44
40161	Zulfiqar	St #3,H # 4,Umar Block G.T Road	60
93569	Amjad	St #3,H # 69,Mian Park	57
6626	M.Arif	St #3,Nawabpura	56
129494	Akram	St #3,Nawabpura	57
101495	Qaiser	St #32,H # 43,Mustafabad	54
47530	Shehzad	St #32,Hussain Pura	41
71465	Naveed	St #33,H # 21,Hajvairy Block	41
72939	Shahid	St #35,H # 5,Mustafabad	41
68518	Sohial	St #36,H # 17,Muslim Abad	60
81780	Hanif	St #36,H # 3,Muslim Abad	58

41993	M.Akram	St #36,H # 3,Muslim Abad	59
23394	Suleman Khan	St #4,H # 1,Dar-UI-Islam	57
42551	Javaid	St #4,H # 37,Razzaq Colony	57
123042	Sadiq	St #4,H #54,A Block Al Faisal Town	48
19531	Basher Ali	St #4,H# 5,Nizambad	45
17499	Irfan	St #41,H # 2,Mustafabad	45
60234	Zeeshan	St #42,H # 109	44
69991	Ashraf	St #42,H # 18,Saraye Ata	44
77359	Akbar	St #45,H # 12,Mustafabad	44
55255	Javaid Iqbal	St #45,H # 18,Mustafabad	56
121568	Faisal	St #45,H # 6,Mustafabad	56
23952	Hashmat Ali	St #45/B,H # 5,Ghaziabad	56
4237	Imtaiz	St #47,H # 1/A,Mojahidabad	56
100022	Noshad	St #47,H # 46,Mujahidaba	56
51950	Abdul Aziz	St #47,H # 46,Mujahidaba	56
58202	Saeed	St #47,H # 50A,Mujahidaba	48
112726	Riaz	St #47,H # 50A,Mujahidaba	48
50477	Shehzad	St #49A,H # 1,Itthad Colony	45
62623	Ishtiaq	St #49A,H # 1,Itthad Colony	45
99464	Zubair	St #49A,H # 64,Itthad Colony	43
126904	Abdul Ghafoor	St #49A,H # 64,Itthad Colony	56
44582	Shafaqat	St #49A,H # 66,Itthad Colony	41
80307	Talib	St #49A,H # 66,Itthad Colony	41
46413	Imdad	St #5,H # 1,Muhammad Pura	58
10131	Sadique	St #5,H # 1,Muhammad Pura	58
82338	Mehar Khan	St #5,H # 2,Shah Din Park	48
3678	Shehzad	St #5,H # 24,A Block Al Faisal Town	45
374	Shahbaz	St #5,H # 3,A Block Al Faisal Town	45
74970	Imran	St #5,H # 70,Muhammad Pura	45
25783	Iftikhar	St #5,H # 70,Muhammad Pura	45
72023	Shabbir	St #5,H # 8,Javaid Colony	60
34624	Sultan	St #50,H # 140,Mojahidabad	57
45498	Agha Khan	St #50,H # 141,Mojahidabad	45
114200	Ishfaq	St #52,H # 11,Mujahidaba	44
46056	Manzoor	St #52,H # 2,Military Accounts Colony	59
75886	Gulzar	St #52,H # 2,Mustafabad	58
59676	Younas	St #52,H # 42,Mojahidabad	56
108305	Tariq	St #53,H # 21	45
100379	Tanvir	St #54,H # 212,Mojahidabad	45
22836	Khadim Hussain	St #54,H # 219,Mojahidabad	43
80865	Aslam	St #56,H # 257,Mojahidabad	43
8099	Kashif	St #56,H # 257,Mojahidabad	43
125073	Ibrar	St #56,H # 29,Mojahidabad	56
114758	Adrees	St #56,H # 29,Mojahidabad	58
7742	Hassan Shah	St #57,H # 216,Mojahidabad	56
52866	Yaseen	St #6, Bhutto Colony	45
92096	Anwar	St #6,H # 151,Mian Park	45
11047	Abid	St #6,H # 2 A Block Al Faisal Town	45
116232	Rasheed	St #6,H # 5,Rasool Pura	58
3321	Manzoor	St #6,H # 5,Rasool Pura	58

66129	Abas	St #6,H # 7,Awami Bhaithak	58
52308	Khushi	St #6,H # 83-A,Mustafabad	58
130410	Rizwan-Ul-Haq	St #6,H #6,Rasheed Pura	56
135389	Shakeel	St #6,H #6,Rasheed Pura	56
83812	Shahid	St #63,Ganda Nala	54
137220	Nawaz	St #63,Ganda Nala	56
13636	Ayas	St #63,Ganda Nala	56
35183	Arif	St #63,Ganda Nala	56
7184	Hamayun	St #64,H # 17,Ganda Nala	58
91180	Mazhar Ali	St #7,H # 17,Tajpura	56
115115	Mubarak	St #7,H # 3,Deen Muhammad Colony	44
116589	Mukhtar	St #7,H #1, Takyia Mondra	58
112168	M.ljaz	St #9,B Block Al Faisal Town	56
125431	Nadeem	St 4h# 59 Imam Town	56
49003	Asif	St# 11 H# 24 Gulshan Park	44
67044	Mehmood Ahmed	St# 11 H# 5 Maskeen Pura	43
86201	Sadiq	St# 12 H# 65 Gulshan Park	56
28730	Islam	St# 1h# 3 Amma Town	44
63181	Imtiaz	St# 3 H# 13 Amma Town	43
61150	Hanif	St# 49/B,H # 49,Shalimar Scheme	43
103884	Boota	St# 6,H # 17,Takiya Mondran	60
113642	Naseem Akhtar	St#1 h#1 gull kali	59
121010	Younas	St#10 H#12 Ithad Town	58
98906	Ishfaq Ahmed	St#10 H#2/C Gunj Bazaar	56
27256	Younas	St#10 H#23 Bismillah Chowk	56
67602	Raza	St#11 H#2 Faisal Park	44
47887	Naseer Ahmed	St#11 h#59 block C	44
5710	Sajjad	St#11 H#9 Doghaj Town	44
95601	Nadeem	St#11 H324 Gulshan Park	44
101853	Haroon	St#12 H#65 Gulshan Park	44
18415	M.Latif	St#16 H#165 Qadir Bakhsh Park	44
94127	M.Rafique	St#19 h3179 saray jouray pul	44
106274	Younas	St#2 h#2 Gulshan park	44
5152	Fiaz	St#2 H#2 Zohra Colony	44
133915	Shafique	St#2 H#3 Haji Takiya Shah	44
88233	Ghullam Ali	St#2 H#3 Zohra Colony	56
123957	Shahid	St#2 H#39 Habib Park	56
53424	Bashir	St#20 H#16 Block D	44
53781	Qasim	St#21 andron chubacha h#85	56
125989	M.Sharif	St#21 h#51warispura	44
10689	Atif	St#21 h389 andron chubbacha	45
44024	Ishfaq	St#25 H#12 Gunj Bazaar	43
118621	Mukhtar	St#26 H#2 Wali Park	56
32793	Gafoor	St#26 H#48 Gunj Bazaar	43
115673	Shahid	St#27 H#25 Main Fateh Garh	43
41635	Ghullam Ali	St#28 H#8 Muhallah Murad Pura	56
89148	Asghar Sindhu	St#3 h#16 hira colony	43
19888	Allah Rakha	St#3 h#18 gulshan farooq scheme	43
89706	Lehar Assaib	St#3 h#29 Hira Colony	56
119536	Zeeshan	St#35 H#184	56

103326	Taj Deen	St#3h#4 Faisal Park	44
13994	Sardar	St#4 H#1 Razaq Colony	56
107390	M.Asiam	St#4 H#2 Badar Colony	43
29846	Abdul Gafoor	St#4 h#3 gulshan park	43
124515	Saeed	St#4 H#36 Razaq Colony	44
15110	Farrukh	St#4 H#4 Ramzan Park	44
30762	Abdusattar	St#4 H#9 Block A Al Faisal Town	48
20446	Abdul Wahid	St#44 h#24 gunj mughalpura	56
51392	Basher Ahmed	St#5 H#3 Muhallad Murad Pura	57
96516	Abdul Latif	St#55 H#208	43
135746	Sajjad Akhtar	St#6 H#5 Razaq Colony	43
18057	Rasheed	St#7 Badar Colony H#24	44
21920	Muhammad Ali	St#7 h#123 andron chubacha	54
46971	Munir Ahmed	St#7 H#21 Faisal Park	56
109779	Shoukat	St#8 H#19 Muhallah Murad Pura	56
95958	Waseem	St#8 H#6 lthad Town	56
36098	Abdul Jabbar	St#8 H#6 Muhallah Murad Pura	59
41077	Fiaz Ahmed	St#8 H#7 Muhallah Murad Pura	44
127462	Ilyas	St#9 H#09 Kotly Peer Abdul Rehman	44
6268	Arif	St#9 H#18 Dharampura	44
57287	Asghar	St#9 h#9 gunj mughalpura	44
78833	Zulfiqar	Street 3/B,H # 41	56
50834	Shehzad	Takya Mondra	56
134830	Ishfaq	Umar Colony	56
122126	Aftab	Usman Nagar Bazaar No.5	44
123600	Nisar	Waada Hospital Canal Bank Scheme	44
119179	Basher	Zubair Block St#12 H#28	44
132441	Fareed	St # 2,Qalandar Pura	56
92654	Sohail	St # 56,H # 20,Ittihad Colony	41
110695	Iftikhar	St # 57,H # 225,Mojahidabad	41
129852	Yousaf	St # 57,H # 252,Mojahidabad	41
35741	Ahsan	St #7,Deen Muhammd Colony	58
106832	Rafique	St #7,H # 4,Bhutto Colony	43
104800	Kashif	St #7,H # 8,Deen Muhammad Colony	43
9573	Riaz	St # 25,Gulshan Park	60
120652	Sajid	St # 31,H # 24,Nima Wala Bazaar No.1	60
128020	Asif	St #11,H # 9,Taj Bagh	45
105916	Abdulatif	St #53,H # 10,Mian Meer	45
34267	Akram	St # 26,H # 25,Wali Park	56
111253	M.Saleem	St # 7,H # 5,A Block Al Faisal Town	55
54898	Ashraf	Ahata No.260,Allama Iqbal Road	44
49361	Ghullam Mustafa	H # 15,Olympic Clinic	55
1289	Amir	H # 21,Umar Colony	56
108863	Ghullam Mustafa	H#427 St#39	55
25425	Amir	Kharan Wala Mohallah Fateh Garh	56
137778	Khursheed Ahmed	St # 3,H # 9 ,Rasool Pura	58
113284	Saif	St # 44,H # 12 Suk Nehar	54
12163	Shafique	St # 5,H # 3,Nishter Town Darogawala	48
39603	Ashraf	St #49,H # 63,Ittihad Colony Ghaziabad	44
131883	Ali	St # 1 H # 4 Ghosia Colony	54

9.7 PILOT STUDY, LIST OF HOUSEHOLDS.

The pilot study of the current research was the first step of the practical application. The latter is also called a ‘feasibility’ study. It can also be a specific pre-testing of research instruments, including questionnaires or interview. It was done on 10% of the study population i.e 40 respondents who were households residing in the same area but were not the part of the study sample. As no changes were made in questionnaire or methodology after the pilot study. Therefore, the main study was conducted.

Saleembuitt	Street No 5 House 10 Ghazi Peep Darbar
Kursheed	House No 16 Faheed Park
Mushtaq	Androonchaubacha House 97
Ajmal	8 Riazpooralahore
Shaukat	House No 8 Qalandarpoora
Ameerhamza	Amil Town Banglow No 6
Hanif	20 Street 36 D Block Al Faisal Town
Rasheed Khan	Street 104 Androonchaubacha
Mehmood	House B232 Bhatta Street
Pappo	Street24 House 15 Doger Road
Ramzan	Street 26 House 2 Wali Park
Hussain	House 1 Wali Park Street25
Islam	Street 26 House 515 Gulistan Colony
Sajjad	Mustaffabad House 80 Street 27
Ashraf	Street2 28 House 4 Muradpura
Fazal	Banglow 6 Qureshimohalla
Mohdazhar	Street 3 B Block Qalandarpura
Nasir	Takyamondran House No 1
Khalid	Street 3 House 15 Ghazi Peer Darbar
Sadiq M	Street 3 House 20 Immam Town
Mehboob	21 Alfaisal Town House 21 Street 3
Akbarali	Street 3 House 24 Mian Park
Nasir	Street 3 House 3 Janazgah
Kashif	Qalandarpura House No 5
Safdar	House 56 Street 3 Mustafabad
Mohdlatif	Street 3 Hoise 5 Ganj Bazar
Mohdali	Ghosia Colony House 7 Street 3
Fahad	Noor Colony Hpouse 9 Dstreet 3
Sadiq	Fatehgarh Street 30 House 102
Shabbier	Street 31 House 11 Chandjewellers wali Gali
Sohail	Street 31 House2 Nimawala Bazar
Shaukat	Rashidpurastreet 31
Azeem	Street 32 House 12 Main Bazar Dharampura
Akbar	Hussainpura Street 32 House No 8
Alihamza	Mustaffabad House 26 Street 32
Shafiq	Hussainpura Street 32
Asmat	Street 33 House 4 Usman Block House 4 Choungigujjarpura
Sajjad	Street 36 Hopuse 3 Ganj Bazar